

An Overview of Problems and Difficulties with ML in WSNs Protection

Dr. Piyush Raja ✉

Global Educator, RAM Literature and Research Foundation, Bihar, India

Dr. Amit Kumar

Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Applications,
Gaya College, Gaya, Bihar, India

Dr. Ram Krishna Kumar

Co-Founder, RAM Literature and Research Foundation, Bihar, India

Dr. Birendra Goswami

Professor, Department of Computer Applications,
Sai Nath University, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India

ABSTRACT:

There are serious, mutually exclusive problems with resources and security in wireless sensor networks. As security complexity rises, battery consumption will follow suit. It is useless to rely on the security of common protocols like encryption and key management because of the limited capacity of wireless sensor networks and their dynamic architecture. Algorithms for machine learning are one of the proposed ways to combine judgment, awareness and observation to deliver intelligence services in this kind of network. Machine learning algorithms provide new issues related to training and the amount of data required for training. This paper neatly covers the architecture of wireless sensor networks as well as the security challenges they face. It also goes into the challenges and recommended fixes for improving sensors' ability to identify dangers, assaults, hazards, and suspicious activity via their ability to learn and grow on their own using machine learning techniques. This might be achieved by reducing the cost of WSNs across several domains. This research also addresses open issues with machine learning algorithms that are pertinent to adapting them to the properties of sensors inside that kind of network.

Keywords: ML, WSNs, WSNs Security, ZigBee.

Suggested Citation: P. Raja, A. Kumar, R.K. Kumar, B. Goswami, "An Overview of Problems and Difficulties with ML in WSNs Protection," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 245-278, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).18](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).18)

INTRODUCTION

WSN is a term used to refer to a collection of different distributed sensors. The major two applications that the WSN are utilized for are monitoring and tracking. The goal of the sensor node, in particular, in WSN tracking applications is to follow the animal, adversary, person, traffic, automobile, or bus, while in WSN monitoring applications, the sensor node monitors the environment, patient movement, and security detection, among other things.

User must overcome a number of obstacles before developing an application employing sensor network technology, including design and deployment, localization, data aggregation and sensor fusion, energy-aware routing and clustering, scheduling, security, and quality of service.

Large-scale sensors may be used in this industry in the near future due to the MEMS technology's fast advancement. Large-scale sensor networks must, however, inevitably bring a lot of data into

WSNs for processing, transmission, and reception. Due to the energy and bandwidth limitations of the sensor, it is simply not feasible to transmit all data back to a base station for processing and drawing conclusions. As a result, ML methods must be used in WSNs. ML algorithms quickly adjust their behavior by iteratively learning the characteristics of the environment. ML methods utilized in WSNs generally include neural networks, fuzzy logic, evolutionary algorithms, reinforcement learning, and swarm intelligence. These algorithms might effectively use the distributive property of WSNs while reducing the quantity of data transmissions.

Consequently, in order to maximize the benefits of these WSNs, such WSN nodes require a control system capable of controlling both their interactions with each other and along with base station.

For instance, the Internet Technical Team established the ZigBee [4] and 6LoWPAN [5] technologies for conventional transmission over IEEE 802.15.4, which both allow administration in WSNs. Those protocols allow for the usage of IEEE 802.15.4 in the 2.4 GHz band and short transmission [6]. For instance, depending on IP addresses on various tiers, 6LoWPAN IPv6 offers a link between WSNs. The network architecture is also mapped using the 6LoWPAN Reduced Energy and Losses Networks standard, and the WSN communication is secured using the AES encryption technique [7]. These networks' dynamic topologies, however, will affect network routing techniques, latency, multi-layer architecture, coverage, Quality of Services (QoS), and fault diagnosis [8]. Due to the nature of the contexts when those wearable sensors are created, it's indeed imperative to reevaluate the administration of WSNs by creating or implementing new protocols.

One of the most significant problems with WSNs is security, which severely impacts energy usage. A node's power consumption rises with the complexity of a WSN's security, and vice versa. One of the problems that new researches in this sector are tackling is the necessity for both (lowering security and energy usage) given the difficult settings in which these sensors may function [9, 10]. Additionally, it is necessary to reevaluate the employment of the conventional security procedures, which are known as the Triangle and characterized by Confidentiality, Integration, and Authentication (CIA) [11]. Traditional procedures include key exchange and encryption as well as the act of encrypting data between two communication devices (two nodes) [12]. The frequent shifting of network topologies brought on by the constant movement of WSN nodes, as we indicated in the previous paragraph, makes these technologies energy-intensive approaches. Therefore, simpler and quicker alternatives are needed, and this is what is being looked for. Thus, one of the techniques that may be employed for this purpose is artificial intelligence algorithms. A node may learn how to communicate with other nearby WSN nodes, look for viruses, examine incoming and outgoing packets, establish node-to-node authentication, and maintain availability [13].

One of the most well-known applications of artificial intelligence is machine learning (ML), in which computers create a mathematical model from a sample of data (referred to as "training data") in order to make predictions or judgments without being explicitly instructed to do so [15]. The mentioned justifications make the ML nature of WSNs appropriate: Due to the complexity of WSN ecosystems, mathematical frameworks cannot be created. Additionally, some applications employ data sets that need to be integrated in order for them to work effectively. Finally, in keeping with the nature of WSNs, ML algorithms do not need human involvement [16]. WSNs also exhibit surprising dynamics and behaviors. The resources and computing capabilities of nodes, as well as the need for large data sets for learning, provide the two key obstacles to ML in WSNs. The difficulty of applying ML algorithms to the integrity and confidentiality of security requirements is one of the most significant issues encountered by ML algorithms with regard to the security of WSN networks. Therefore, machine learning techniques may aid in improving wireless network security, decreasing all types of congestion issues [17–19], and assisting with physical layer authentication procedures [20–22] and error detection [23–25]. Additionally, ML algorithms have a significant advantage in packet analysis between WSN nodes and the identification of suspect nodes [26].

The use of machine learning algorithms in many aspects of wireless sensor networks and the Internet of Things was covered in several studies (IoT). As an example, writers in [13, 16, 27] spoke about the use of ML algorithms in various WSN applications. Additionally, several writers in [15, 28–31] spoke about ML algorithms in security sub-domains including congested traffic and intrusion detection in IoT and WSN. Others have explored the security needs of WSNs, such [32]. However, none of the research that was examined addressed the usage of ML algorithms to provide WSNs

with security criteria at every tier. As a result, this paper gives a thorough explanation of the security needs of the WSN as well as the role that ML algorithms play in meeting these criteria across all WSN levels. In comparison to the conventional ways represented by data encryption, ML algorithms may provide a superior solution for the protection of wireless sensor networks. The issues that WSNs may encounter while applying Learning algorithms will also be covered in this article, along with solutions. Additionally, it makes suggestions for ways to make it possible to use ML algorithms on many levels at once to protect wireless sensor networks. Additionally, it offers a statistical analysis of each security architecture in WSNs that ML algorithms often implement. The following is a summary of this paper's important efforts:

- a. We provide a thorough explanation of the security criteria met by Machine learning algorithms in the context of existing WSN encryption methods.
- b. In order to increase the privacy of WSNs through machine learning approaches, we give a systematic and thorough evaluation of the most recent technologies in the literature. Each technique's advantages and disadvantages are also mentioned.
- c. We discuss the limits of employing ML in existing security solutions for WSNs, the difficulties in securing them, and potential future research solutions.

The breadth of this research and how it was classified are shown in Figure 1's graphic. We briefly describe the infrastructure of WSNs in Section 2, then talk about risks and security needs. The ML methods utilized in WSN security are discussed in Section 3. A wireless sensor network's security issues are covered in Section 4, and current research that have been conducted to address these difficulties are covered in Section 5. After that, Section 6 discusses unresolved concerns concerning the protection of the WSNs and the function of ML in its future evolution. The paper is finally concluded in Section 7.

Figure 1. Show the Classification Used in This Study

INFORMATION ABOUT WSN

As the fundamental component of the Internet of Things (IoT) technological concept, the wireless sensor network is the subject of this section's discussion. This tool is used to carry out all kinds of

fieldwork, including data collecting in all of its forms as well as observation, scanning, as well as other tasks. Thus, we cover their kinds, money methods, restrictions, and data security via them in this part.

Overview of WSN

Global awareness, sophisticated processing, and dependable information conveyance are the IoT's main benefits. Realizing how information is shared between devices or between humans and devices is crucial. These gadgets, which effectively communicate in many settings to enable the IoT, include embedded systems, control and automation systems, wireless sensor networks, and others [33]. As a result, data may be transported across several networks without the involvement of a person. The smart city and house are the most common sectors in the actual world of IoT applications. Perception, the network, and the application are the three layers that make up these apps [34]. The perception layer is implemented in a low-power WSN, whereas the network and application layers are implemented in high-power devices that will protect data. The WSN is made up of several sensor nodes that may conduct a variety of sensing, surveillance, measuring, and tracking functions and can communicate with one another utilizing various radio frequencies [35]. These resource-constrained wireless nodes exhibit poor processing power, confined bandwidth, short battery life, and constrained memory capacity [9]. Figure 2 shows the interaction between WSN layers.

Figure 2. Shows How the WSN Layers Interact with One Another

In order to maintain the network architecture, wireless sensor networks are in charge of displaying the topology of the network and modifying the forwarding information in the perceptual layer [6]. The Proposed system then begins gathering information from various sources and transmitting it over to the network layer. The Wireless sensor networks serve as the fundamental component of that kind of layer and have several features in common with the other wireless connections [36]. These qualities include the number of things:

- a. Autonomous nodes devoid of a centralized power
- b. Fixed or moving WSN nodes
- c. WSN nodes' communication range is likewise constrained.
- d. The architecture of the WSNs is continually evolving.
- e. Connectivity with several hops
- f. Limitations on bandwidth

From the other hand, WSN nodes may often function in untrusted, seldom monitored contexts. Due to this flaw, sensitive information may be readily exposed to unauthorised parties, raising serious safety and security concerns [37].

Two popular technologies that provide administration in Wsn applications at the network layers are ZigBee and 6LoWPAN [3]. Additionally, they can adjust to a variety of alternative network media, including Bluetooth [39], sub-1 GHz radio frequency [6], low-power Wi-Fi [38], and Wi-Fi [39]. Additionally, 6LoWPAN and ZigBee were contrasted in [40], with 6LoWPAN offering IP capabilities for WPAN networks and ZigBee offering many low-cost, low-power nodes. Additionally, ZigBee may be utilised for smart metres, home area networks, and other devices that can be remotely monitored intelligently. ZigBee employs robust encryption technologies and a dependable security mechanism to protect its data. Furthermore, its network technology is more efficient than other systems since it avoids channel collisions. Contrarily, 6LoWPAN is ideal for low-power Internet protocol systems like sensors. Figure 3 depicts a summary of the key components of the architecture for these innovations.

Figure 3. Shows WSN Controlling Procedures

Sensor nodes are, though, constrained by computational power and energy in the perception layers of both protocols [41]. It may be challenging to provide a charger in some of those areas since the WSN is designed to function in a range of settings. Either the battery's capacity should be increased, or the security standards should be relaxed, to get around this restriction [42]. Renewable energy sources including heat, wind, and light may also be used to power nodes [43]. Because of the size of the WSN and the need for extra hardware, these options, however, seem to be out of reach. However, lowering security standards makes data breaches possible [44].

Applications of WSNs

The military [45], healthcare monitoring [46], factory equipment [47], and smart homes [48] are just a few of the application areas where WSNs are deployed [49]. A protocol dubbed "Thread" that flawlessly links and manages smart home appliances and runs across Layer 6LoW- PAN has been tried to be standardized by more than 50 firms [50]. Figure 4 displays the majority of these kinds of WSNs implementations [51].

Furthermore, hackers may swiftly inject, intercept, redirect, and modify overhead connections because of the nature of broadcasting and wireless network vulnerabilities [52]. This may be dangerous, particularly when networking is used for medical purposes [9], military purposes [53,54], or the identification of human targets [55]. Any security breach might have serious repercussions. Therefore, when employed in healthcare, WSNs might be quite interesting for the civilian sector. However, these networks must be adequately protected from all types of security risks and assaults because they include sensitive data [53]. Along with the data's accessibility, one aspect that must be maintained is the data's ongoing flow.

Figure 4. Shows Applications of WSNs

Security in WSNs

Numerous studies have tackled security issues in WSN administration protocols using the Confidentiality, Integrity, and Authentication Triangle (CIA). This triangle represents the three axes that every network must satisfy in order to be deemed secure. Maintaining confidentiality involves protecting the privacy of significant data sent between WSN nodes. Important packet segments are often encrypted before being sent from the transmitting node, and they are subsequently decrypted at the node that received the packet [11]. The network has to be ready to prevent attackers from changing the messages transmitted under the integrity condition. Attackers have the ability to alter their poles using interference beams. Furthermore, a rogue routing node has the ability to alter crucial packet data prior to forwarding. Availability is the last prerequisite for completing the security triangle. Availability is the WSN Services' readiness to be used whenever it is needed. In any instance, attackers may launch attacks that compromise network security or completely take down the network. Denial of Service (DoS) is the most dangerous threat to network availability [56]; it occurs when attackers prevent the network from setting up services by delivering wireless interference, interfering with network protocols, or wearing down WSN nodes in different ways. The discussion of this assault type will follow.

The User Datagram Protocol (UDP), which is often used for the transport layer in 6LoWPAN, may be layered with the Datagram Transportation Layer Security protocol to provide data security [57]. The AES-128 method is used for link-layer authentication and encryption, and TLS is run through the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) [2]. To continue the usage of sophisticated encryption procedures, the TLS/DTLS implementation needs extra hardware encryption hardware [58]. Additionally, since these protocols have high overhead costs and resource requirements, it is challenging to incorporate Internet Protocol security (IPSec), which is often employed at the network layer, and Transport Layer Security (TLS), into the applications of such networks [59]. Due to the WSN devices' usage of wireless communication within the boundaries of open communication channels, these solutions are also unable to completely fulfil the Security Triangle (CIA) [60]. So that these kinds of networks may operate successfully in their settings and defend against any harmful assaults, a group of protocols must cooperate. Malicious attacks are categorized into categories in the context of WSN security [44, 61], and each category affects sensor nodes differently depending on the level to which it belongs. Figure 4 displays how these groupings are distributed throughout the WSN model's tiers.

According to Figure 5, although the DoS attack uses all levels, there are several harmful assaults in each layer. DoS attacks, jamming, exhaustion, and collisions interfere with network availability and connection. Contrarily, confidentiality and integrity are threatened by Sybil, Hole, Spoofing, Session hijacking, Eavesdropping, Man in the Middle, and Selective forwarding [62]. Additionally, although certain assaults may occur in both active and passive stages, those that target connection and availability are classified as active attacks.

In terms of data management and transmission reliability between network nodes, each of these levels is responsible for certain duties. The physical layer improves dependability by lessening the impact of shadowing and path loss. The communication between WSN nodes must be compatible at the data link layer via fault detection and multiplexing [21]. Additionally, the network layer will provide the most efficient path for data transmission to the edge router. However, each WSN node serves as a router in a WSN, and the security associated with this layer is in charge of protecting this path from intrusions. Additionally, the application layer is in charge of maintaining, gathering, and processing data to provide reliable results, while the transport layer is in charge of sending data to external networks [32].

Figure 5. Classifies Malicious Assaults

Another significant problem in the WSN security realm is authentication. For instance, the authentication mechanism seeks to prevent unauthorized WSN nodes from taking use of the WSN network. In addition to these fundamental needs for safeguarding the security of wireless networks and those who interact with them, numerous encryption and decryption techniques are utilized in the security sector, while the limits of WSNs drive research into diverse security technologies [63]. In order to offer information on the circumstances of a breach, it is also necessary to monitor the activities of linked WSN devices. As a result, non-repudiation is necessary for network security in order to demonstrate behaviors for each WSN device [63]. Additionally, physical entrance is simple because of the hostile environment and illegal access to the network is quicker in a WSN setting than it is through a wired connection. If such user authentication is permitted, not only would network performance suffer, but there is also a chance that data security may be jeopardized. Access control and parsing are necessary to prevent this, and they may be supplied by a number of access control rules and encryption techniques [59].

Attacks on WSNs

Figure 5 illustrates how multiple malicious WSN attacks impact both power and CPU use in addition to security concerns. Therefore, compared to other forms of networks, these sorts of networks must place a greater emphasis on coming up with workable and practical solutions. We go into great depth on how each kind of assault impacts WSNs.

1. Listening in

The security-related limitations of WSNs (such as hostile environment, dynamic nodes, and unreliable communication) make it easier for hackers to eavesdrop on information being transmitted between nodes, which increase the impact of radio aging and frequency propagation or dispersion [64].

2. Jamming

One of the riskiest forms of attacks for private wireless networks is this one. Despite the dangers, security precautions are often disregarded, which may lead to significant issues if wireless networks are put in place. Due to radio frequency interference, the main effect of jamming is to hinder user service or availability [65].

3. Collision

Since the sensors are spread across many settings, a malicious node replacement corruption might be to blame for this attack. Malicious nodes may interfere with neighbouring broadcasts by sending a short noise packet since they do not follow the Intermediate Access Control Protocol. Despite requiring little energy from the attacker, this attack has the potential to cause significant network failures [66]. Furthermore, pinpointing the origin node is challenging owing to the features of wireless transmission.

4. Injustice

By exploiting contract connection period settings, this kind of attack blocks authorised users from accessing network resources and gets around the submission deadline [67]. Examples of this kind of assault include collision attacks that are repeated or the haphazard exploitation of cooperative media access control layer priority schemes.

5. Weariness

Collision assaults of this kind are repeated until the WSN nodes' entire energy is depleted [66]. As a result of routing loops and route lengthening during packet transfers, resource depletion attacks reduce node energy.

6. Traffic observation

Traffic analysis in WSNs is a method for determining node communication patterns. The study makes advantage of information obtained by monitoring node-to-node communication [68]. This attack particularly targets sink or access point nodes that contain sensitive data and have positional information about those nodes. If the assault succeeds, certain pieces of information are revealed. The system might die as a result of this.

7. A whole assault

During message routing, network layer vulnerabilities called "black holes" or "sink assaults" take place. This destructive bombardment's objective is cluster heads. When a hostile node is designated as the cluster head during this assault, all transactional processes on all of its member nodes are now destroyed. A sinkhole could develop as a consequence [69].

8. Discretionary forwarding

A selective redirection attack is difficult to identify, especially when compromised nodes willfully ignore messages. Hackers may create route discovery that either attracts or eliminates network traffic by using selective redirection. Additionally, they have the power to alter the range of principal routers, transmit false signals, and disregard important information [70].

9. Sybil

The Sybil attack generates many node IDs from a single current node to simulate the presence of a sensor node. In addition, it causes system failure due to problems with resource allocation and other problems. It has a significant impact on load-balancing technologies including shared computing, structure management, and server protocols [31].

10. Faking

This attack targets the transmission of routing data between nodes directly, and it may lead to routing loops, root path expansions and compression, network traceability to or from chosen nodes, network segmentation, fake error messages, and increased end-to-end latency [63].

11. Session exploitation

A cookie side takeover is a different kind of man-in-the-middle attack that gives the attacker total control over the application account. A "session cookie," or a piece of data that identifies the user to the server and allows them access to their account, is sent to you by the app when you log in to an online account, such as Facebook or Twitter. As long as the user's device retains the session token, the server will let them to access the app.

12. Rejecting

When an application or system doesn't have measures in place to properly monitor and record users' activity, hostile tampering or the forging of extra steps may take place. By altering the data authoring of dangerous user activities, this attack may produce inaccurate data that is logged to log files. Its application may be broadened to include general data processing in the name of others, such as email spoofing. If this attack is successful, the data in log files can be thought to be false or misleading [63].

13. Flood

It is an effort to reprogrammed dispersed nodes and is also known as a reprogramming attack. The attacker will be able to take over a significant chunk of the network if the attack is successful. This attack was effective because the bulk of the sensors was placed in a hostile environment and was managed remotely over a wireless network. This may be avoided by using strong authentication.

14. DoS

This kind of attack was used repeatedly across all WSN layers, proving that it can affect any layer. A denial-of-service (DoS) attack aims to take down a system or network, rendering the target audience unable to access it. DoS attacks function by saturating the target with traffic or by supplying information that makes the target fail. Real users (employees, members, or policyholders) are denied access to the services or resources they meant to utilize as a result of a DoS attack [57].

In any event, as network defense software develops, harmful attack methods alter and advance. Therefore, we must harness the abilities of sensors to self-develop in order to preserve the integrity of this kind of wireless network. The adoption of machine learning methods is the ideal choice for their capacity for self-learning. These technologies enable these devices to identify harmful cookies of a novel kind that aren't included in the existing database. The next paragraph goes through the use of machine learning to WSN security.

ML for WSN Security

Sometimes WSNs communicate with access control data inadvertently under malicious conditions. In these circumstances, it is essential to apply WSN data encryption. The security methods may help with information cleanliness, confidentiality, authentication, and integrity. Due to the WSNs' minimal resources and processing power, conventional network security methods like user permission are ineffective for these applications [71]. In order to evaluate IoT malicious network behaviors, for instance, the authors of [72] created an access gateway employing ML classification algorithms including Random Forest, k-NN, and Naive Bayes. Following the results of performance evaluation using various sorts of methodologies, the k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN) method demonstrated the best accuracy. A anonymity the Support Vector Machine training approach for IoT data was also provided by the authors in [73], requiring just two transactions in a single iteration and omitting the need for a trustworthy third party. This method significantly decreased computational complexity when compared to traditional SVM.

Consequently, ML expertise offers a suitable framework for lowering the cost of several security-related domains. For instance, anomaly detection produced great results against all forms of malicious behavior, as well as during packet analysis [64,66,74], tracking, and DoS defense

[20,21,67,75-78]. The ML technique is also used to improve network availability, error detection [23–25], and traffic congestion [17–19]. It may be a useful option in addition to the physical layer's authentication procedures [20–22]. In order to address several of these issues and provide enormous benefits in terms of precision and efficiency, ML approaches are being used in WSNs.

METHODS OF ML

An overview of the several machine learning methods that were applied to WSN safety is given in this section. Various classifications, notably supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement learning, and deep learning, are used to categories these methods. Consequently, under this part, we examine the categories of machine learning techniques that were employed in the research that were evaluated in Section 5. This is due to the fact that many studies have a thorough and functional specialization in machine learning. Figure 6 presents a categorization of the ML algorithms in use.

Here, ML algorithms are briefly outlined; nevertheless, numerous research articles published in this area have studied ML algorithms in great depth.

Figure 6. Shows a Categorization of the ML Techniques Being Used Secure WSNs

Supervised Learning

An ML job known as supervised learning insinuates functionalities using collections of training examples. A collection of base classifiers that each of which comprises of an inputs item and the intended target output, make up the instructional data. The machine learning model is examined by the supervised learning algorithm, which then generates an assumed functionality that may be applied to fresh cases. Whenever the classification name is not accessible, an algorithm with an optimum alternative will still be able to properly recognize the subcategory. The accepted theory is then employed to forecast the confusion matrix [80]. As a result, examples with certain attributes, defined as a training data set, have been used to mathematical modeling. A short summary of the adequate training for supervised learning on information are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Shows Processes of Supervised Learning

Nevertheless, supervised learning has a strong capacity to predict potential samples having high effectiveness and accuracy, but because to its computing requirements during the training procedure, it is challenging to adapt the training program to situations that would request actual conclusions.

These following techniques had made use of this:

1. k-NN

Theoretically, one of the most straightforward machine learning (ML) techniques is the k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN) categorization approach. Throughout this approach, if a pattern's closest different feature neighbors—the most similar k examples—belong to a specific classification, then so does the sample itself. The retraining dataset includes and a fresh entry is used to illustrate the K-nearest approach. This algorithm determines the values as pertaining to this category by identifying the k examples that are the most strongly connected this method detects the values as pertaining to this category by identifying the k examples that are the most strongly connected [82].

2. Decision Tree

With the Decision Tree approach, judgments regarding a specific item are utilised to determine the value that object embodies in the tree's branches. It refers to a technique for predictive modeling which is employed in information retrieval, analytics, and mapping development. Additionally, parameters in different classifiers decisions where another leaflets were portrayed as a tree to perform exactly the symbolize in the branches—contain a collection of numbers. Logistic regressions are data structures which address real-valued numerical variables. Every result of the class label is indeed a resource into the judgement operation, but decision-making originates from continuing decision-making in data mining processes connected to data management [83].

Making a training model that can be used to forecast the category or value of target variables by learning decision rules derived from historical data is the main driver behind utilising a decision tree (training data). In contrast to other classification algorithms, the decision tree approach is thus fairly simple to grasp [84].

3. Random Forest

The Random Forest method increases the projected accuracy of a data set by mixing many decision trees on various subsets. Instead of using a single decision tree to predict the final result, the random forest employs predictions from all of the trees [85]. Accuracy rises and overfitting is minimized in forests with more trees.

4. Supportive Vector Method

A supervised machine learning approach that may be used to Classification issues is the Supporting Vectors Classifier algorithm. The primary use is categorization, where each data piece is assigned a point and its meaning is assigned latitude in an n-dimensional environment. A hyperbolic lines whose characterize different categories is identified in order to identify them. Everything that was said is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Shows SVM Method

5. Naive Bayes

The naive Bayes categorization approach relies upon that autonomous assumptions of unique circumstances as well as the Bayes theorem. Researchers initially determine the combination information posterior density for a particular training set of information using the independence hypotheses of showcase characteristics. Next, utilising this modeling, researchers use Bayes' theorem to determine the outputs with said highest likelihood of occurring in the future for the given set of inputs y [87]. In greater detail, a collection of learning data that demonstrates the predicted class based on the elements ought to be utilized to training this classification. Even during training process, the function generates its clusters for this piece of data, but instead uses those a third attempt to classify a predicted collected data. The naive Bayes classifier's supervised structure makes the assumption that perhaps the classifications in the having to learn information are recognized and supplied [88].

6. ANN

The information classification method based on a representation of individual neurons is known as an Artificial Neural Network. A vast quantity of neurons make up an ANN, which processes input and produces accurate results. In ANN, layers are often utilized, and nodes are used to link the layers, with each node serving a combat service [89]. A processing unit, one or more concealed, and more production layer are the 3 parts that make up an ANN. Unlike other classification algorithms, ANN has no input constraints and performs very well when categorizing complicated and non-linear data sets.

7. Logistic Regression

A collection of quantitative or qualitative descriptive parameters may be used to estimate or characterize the values used by a qualitative attribute value using the statistical approach known as logistic regression (LR) (most typically binary). LR is also characterised as a method for matching a regression model to the data when the dependent variable is dichotomous [90]. This approach is used in research to determine if the independent factors can predict a dichotomous dependent variable.

8. Least-Mean-Square

A form of ML filter that uses stochastic gradient descent in complex terms is the least mean square (LMS) approach. To estimate the output, gradient descent is employed to continuously update the filter weights. Moreover, the idea of algorithm convergence makes LMS need certain learning curves in ML theory and practise. These concepts centre on refining ML models, tying inputs and outputs together, enhancing training and testing procedures, and generally establishing "convergence"—the state in which a recurrent learning process converges rather than deviates—[91].

9. Bayesian

Statistical learning techniques are the foundation of the Bayesian supervised machine learning approach [50]. Bayesian learning finds relationships between datasets by learning conditional independence using various statistical techniques. A group of inputs $X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n$ provide the chance $p(X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n)$ to be maximised. Additionally, Bayesian learning may be utilised with multiple probability functions for various class node factors [90].

Unsupervised Learning

One of the main subfields of machine learning and artificial neural networks is unsupervised learning. Machine learning algorithms are taught by identifying data patterns without being aware of the data's outcome. Estimating data density to identify similarities between objects and statistically organize them is one of the main uses of unsupervised learning. Additionally, when compared to supervise learning, it can be claimed that the distinction between the two is that the former aims to infer the original distribution of data, whilst the latter attempts to do so from extra parameters [92].

Unsupervised learning, however, offers less complexity and takes less time to implement, but the output prediction's accuracy suffers.

These types of algorithms have been applied:

1. K-Means

A machine learning approach called k-means clustering divides nearby points into clusters. Because the new point in each group is challenged based on its distance from all other groups (typically its distance from the group centre or its arithmetic mean) and put into the group to which it is closest, this approach does not develop a learning model. For instance, creating a line of three groups to divide a set of points. It will utilise a measurement of how distant a point is from the group to calculate how near a point is to that group (for example, the distance between two points) [93].

2. Fuzzy Logic

With the fuzzy group giving a degree of membership to the universe's elements, which is typically a real number with a period of [0, 1], fuzzy logic aims to insert values (degrees) between real numbers (elements). Fuzzy logic is created when degrees of truth are assigned to propositions. The current scale for truth values (scores) is [0, 1], where 0 stands for "totally untrue," 1 for "absolutely true," and the other numbers represent partial truth, or degrees of truth in between [94]. Fuzzy logic is thus used to tackle problems including uncertainty, estimations, ambiguity, qualitative chaos, and partial truth.

Deep Learning

Deep learning is a subtype of ANN classification technology, and deep learning approaches are ways to describe data learning using multi-layer representation. Figure 9 provides an illustration of the deep learning approach. It consists of fundamental non-linear modules that move the description from a lower to a higher layer in order to get the best outcome [95]. Deep learning can extract high-level properties from data, work with or without labels, and be taught to accomplish a variety of objectives, among other benefits.

Figure 9. Shows Techniques of Deep Learning

These types of algorithms have been employed:

1. CNN

At their core, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are multi-layer Perceptron-like deep learning algorithms, although they acquire different things, are constructed differently, and serve different purposes. Additionally, CNNs are frequently employed in a wide range of scenarios via data analysis. This procedure of determining and gathering characteristic choices are carried out in the initial

phase, followed by the svm classifier [96]. One or even more convolutions that harvest the properties from videos or photos and a completely connected layer that creates the required output are its distinguishing features [97]. The method is comprised of many sections, beginning with both the convolution operation and progressing through the activation mechanism, cushioning layer, average pooling, and substantially associated layer. Additionally, every stratum is arranged in a distinctive form. The whole primary pattern contains horizontal line; the second indicates angles, then so on. These elements build upon one another before their intended purpose is fully clear. This CNN algorithm's construction technique is depicted in Figure 10 [98].

2. RNN

Recurring Neural Networks (RNN) are utilized in a variety of industries, including computational linguistics, genetic information alteration, and several others. These specialize in comprehending and modifying repetitions of various forms. Additionally, RNNs contain such a storage that enables devices to use knowledge from earlier inputs to modify present input and output. Its outcome in RNNs relies on the preceding items inside the data set, in contrast to certain other deep neural networks which presume that perhaps the intakes and outcomes are autonomous [99]. The RNN, on the contrary hand, struggles with selective memories. If indeed the series is lengthy sufficiently, this will likely have trouble moving information between previous generations stages to later periods.

Figure 10. Shows CNN Architecture

3. Long-Term Short Memory

A unique kind of RNN called long-term memory is capable of learning reliant long-term knowledge. LSTMs were created expressly to address the issue of long-term reliance. The fundamental idea of LSTMs is gateways. The condition of the cell serves as a route for conveying relevant information throughout the chain, acting as a sort of development of information. It may be regarded as the broadcaster's "memory." The sequence of events may be impacted by the condition of the cell. As a result, even information from earlier period stages may transfer to later ones, lessening the impact of poor fuse on acquisition and recollection of information. Even as cell moves, data is put into it or taken from that too [100]. Nevertheless, different neural networks are in charge of controlling state vector information.

4. Multi-Layer Perceptron

An example of a network that consists network is the number of convolution. Due to its multiple layer upon layer and semi stimulation, a quadratic auto encoder may detect data that cannot be linearly separated. The MLP does have a receptive field, a dense nodes, and a convolution layers, which represents the minimum number of node divisions. With the exception of the input layers, it is a neuronal that employs a nonlinear function. Additionally, MLP employs training algorithm, a supervised machine learning method, for retraining [101].

5. Back propagation Neural Networks

During deep convolutional neural networks, back propagation, also known as reactionary interferences, is a common method for computing variations. It is used in a number of supervised learning methods, notably gradient descent, and building refers to cooperative neural networks. A human brain that is being trained via back propagation will determine its loss rate, which is the discrepancy amongst their projections and the actual classifications. We may calculate the output error for every load in the connection using convolutions. By revising each component independently, the regression model may be decreased across a large number of model workouts [102].

Training algorithm, which goes retrograde it through patch antenna out from final layer to the original layer, is therefore an opposite of gradients calculation. Algebra uses the transform to aggregate the distinctions of all succeeding layers and ascertain the variation in a certain stratum.

WSNS SECURITY ISSUES

The Challenges of WSNs Security

Technology for WSNs allows for effective data collecting and real-time data transfer via the perception layer. This layer imposes restrictions on the network architecture as a whole, notably because of its dependence on open wireless channels.

There are various difficulties, particularly in the area of security, based on the features of the WSN nodes outlined above. Data safety and confidentiality in WSNs are a concern as well; given how difficult it is to execute the network security standards outlined earlier on WSNs. The primary difficulties with WSNs security are shown in Figure 11, and we go through these issues below:

Figure 11. Shows Security Challenges of WSNs

1. Lack of Consolidated Control

As a result of the perception layer's lack of centralization, individual authentication processes, for instance, will take place between neighboring WSN nodes. Therefore, using protocols based on grouping WSN nodes into clusters and allowing nearby WSN nodes to share the same authentication is a workable option [9].

2. WSNs Topology Changes

The WSN network architecture is constantly changing as a result of WSN node mobility, environmental changes, the acquisition of new WSN nodes, or the loss of existing WSN nodes [103]. Routing and authentication systems that support multi-hop communication are two examples of protocols that cope with these topological changes. For instance, each time the network architecture

is updated, the information is exchanged between both the sending WSN node and any other WSN nodes within the transmitter's broadcast range.

3. Scalable Trust Management

Trust management in WSNs refers to the challenge of differentiating between real and fraudulent nodes. Energy considerations, the number of nodes to take into account, the possibility of a violation and the requirement to revoke trust when it is identified, as well as the difficulty of reestablishing confidence when breaches occur are all particular difficulties to credibility in sensor network administration [104]. Furthermore, it may not be possible to implement sophisticated key evolutionary algorithms or pairings between them owing to the performance/energy limitations of certain of the WSN nodes. Even if it is possible to accomplish something once, it may not be feasible to do it again.

Limits on the number of nodes exchanging keys need to be implemented in order to lessen the effect of an assault as it is expected that a physical penetration of certain WSN nodes is unavoidable. The procedure may be carried out by creating simple key management techniques [105].

Additionally, in order to transmit and receive data from and to other nodes in the WSN, each node has to have a certain degree of confidence from its neighbours. When building the network's architecture or when transmitting and receiving data at each node, suspicious packets must be found. To be able to defend itself and its peers, each node needs the Introduction Deduction model, which is accomplished utilising simple self-development abilities.

4. Limited Resources

The WSN node's limited efforts in gathering the data for which this sensor is designed provide additional difficulty. Because of their inability to provide itself with the bare minimum of security, these devices present issues in terms of security, thus it is crucial to minimise their cost in order to meet user demands [106].

Security management in WSNs should be compatible with other network management operations, but it shouldn't need a lot of connections, processing, or storage.

Challenges of Applying ML Algorithms in WSN Security

Despite the significance of machine learning approaches in improving WSN nodes' capacity to detect security flaws or malicious assaults. Due to its low energy and CPU capabilities, this sort of wireless network faces several difficulties [27].

1. ML algorithms, including using initial data acquisition, are unable to produce precise predictions in the moment. The application's effectiveness is dependent on the quantity of supplementary data. When there is a vast volume of data, processing it costs a lot of energy. In these other circumstances, it involves an exchange seen between WSN's constraints as well as the ML computation heavier computational load. Due to overcome these transfer, ML algorithms should always be deployed locally. As a result, those techniques provide a danger [27] in wireless sensor network settings.

2. Not all of the security criteria for WSNs can be satisfied by ML approaches.. Applying techniques to a somewhat access control, such identification and consistency, may occasionally be challenging [107]. Such activities amongst Network elements need a lot of CPU resources. It is challenging to describe this throughout WSN nodes, but it may be expressed, for instance, via identification between the car and the driver [108]. In contrast, several investigations been using this ML algorithms towards development of communication attacks in authenticity [109]. 3. The majority of ML algorithms include a confidence interval, even if it is modest, it still exists. Various ML approaches are explored in Segment 5.2. Consequently, the secrecy of classified material should be almost complete [110]. The Arithmetic Cryptography Model was offered either by researchers in [111] in order to improve specific instance risk management of private health insurance data. Depending on a fuzzy inference technique combined with deep learning, judgment call about the risk management approach in MES was improved. Findings research demonstrates that MES percentage error would be less below 0.05 as well as the detection performance is 97%, which demonstrates their willingness to raise safety concerns. Despite the writers' advancements, there is still some mistake, even though it is almost nil.

USES OF ML TO PROTECT WSN NETWORKS

In this part, we go through how ML algorithms may be used to improve WSN security. Researchers investigate the contribution of ML algorithms in meeting these purposes of collecting upon what has been previously said concerning the potential vulnerabilities in WSNs.

The majority of machine learning (ML) safety technologies have already been employed in intrusion detection systems to better comprehend packet flow in networks [112]. Reducing DDoS and DoS assaults is one way that these ML algorithms contribute to network connectivity. Others, like ransomware assaults, evaluate the behavior of infections and lessen the threats to data integrity [113]. Additionally, several ML methods aid in reducing the risk of identification assaults among WSN nodes. The next chapters will provide a detailed presentation of each of these subcategories.

The Accessibility

Another of the key prerequisites for information security is accessibility. As a result, numerous deliberate or accidental assaults like DoS, asset malfunctions, or electrical problems occur in WSN systems under the guise of dependability. Network availability may be improved using techniques like collision avoidance, vulnerability scanning, and debugging, for instance.

1. Intrusion Detection

The main duties of an intrusion detection system's functions are, in particular, to monitor domains and connections, assess create higher, generate alerts, and respond to odd activity. Although they keep an eye on connected domains and communications, systems that detect intrusions are often installed next to protected network equipment [15]. Since every WSN node functions as a host and a network device, each node must independently carry out the same breach recognition system. The two forms of detection are signature-based and anomaly-based, with anomalies being preferred in terms of teaching skills to WSN nodes. The ML training process, which we discuss in the part on WSN challenges, is still a concern. As a result, several research in this section have tried to enhance the wireless sensor network's machine learning training process by speeding up training, using a smaller data set, and increasing accuracy. The ML methods used for intrusion detection are outlined in Table 4.

In order to enhance DoS detection and reduce power usage in WSNs, authors in [114] presented a novel model. In addition, a brand-new cluster model for the LEACH protocol was suggested by the authors to spread forwarded information across WSN nodes. Thereafter, those who enhanced DDoS Attack detection by using feature selection and a classifier method. Another method for reducing the number of attributes in a dataset is feature selection, which involves choosing the most crucial characteristics for training and discarding the remainder. The authors also tried to calculate the power usage of their suggested approach on WSN and discovered a 5% increase in power consumption. The decision tree, which yields a 100% correct answer, is one of the greatest machine learning strategies for defending wireless sensor networks against DoS, according to the authors. The authors of [115] also investigated the impact of several ML algorithms towards DoS identification in WSNs. To investigate the impact of storage capacity on the instructional phase in ML techniques, they selected ML algorithms of various sorts and deployed them to various dataset sizes. They also researched the WSN nodes' lightweight ML algorithms. According to the findings, datasets of between 3,000 and 6,000 records work best—as long as the proportion of attacked to unattached records is 1:1. The results also demonstrated that the G-boost classifiers, which are part of the logic-based category, are the best classifiers. The top DoS detection system also resulted in a 32% increase in network power usage. Additionally, in the same context as assessing deep learning and conventional machine learning algorithms on wireless sensor network traffic packets. Simple models like (LR, DT, and SVM) are excellent for the effective implications of intrusion detection using deep learning approaches, according to the authors of [86].

The use of statistical analysis has been recommended as a different method for online DoS detection in [116]. The forward-selective and black-hole assaults were carried out by the authors using binary logistic regression. Binary logistic regression was utilized to determine the detection accuracy after a run-time monitor tool was used to aggregate the local WSN node activity, determining whether the packets were malicious or benign. The result of the algorithm was then deployed on the WSN network to track node activity in identifying threats. Their recommendation's accuracy ranged from

96 to 100%. In [117], a different rule-based ML strategy was suggested. To handle ambiguities, inaccuracies, and vagueness, the authors developed hybrid methods that integrate fuzzy logic and other methodologies with a rule-based approach. The dependability of such features was then assessed.

A novel model to increase network lifespan paired with intrusion detection effectiveness was put out by the authors in [75]. The authors suggested an adaptive chicken swarm optimization methodology to reduce a WSN node's power consumption, and they used two tiers of the SVM method for intrusion detection. The SVM will be used to examine packets at the second level after being used to identify the malicious node at the first level. Although the article addressed the problem of extending WSN lifespan, the findings do not provide any justifications for the amount of energy that the suggested solution has saved. The authors of [30] also created a versatile intrusion detection technique using a deep neural network (DNN). The outcomes also showed an increase in the findings' accuracy for various kinds of network traffic. The suggested method's performance accuracy was also described in the study; however it omitted to indicate how much electricity and CPU it would need. Furthermore, by integrating particle swarm optimization (PSO) with the back propagation neural network, the authors in [78] devised a lightweight intrusion detection method for WSN networks (BNN). In order to increase the performance of intrusion detection accuracy, the authors of [118] presented a hybrid feature selection technique in conjunction with a two-level classifier. Furthermore, SVM and MLP were combined in [119] to categories traffic data and find malicious nodes in the WSN network. Some writers have created a hybrid classifier between synthetic sets of machine learning algorithms, going in a different path. A hybrid classifier that blends deep learning with conventional machine learning methods was suggested by the authors in [120]. To enhance intrusion detection in WSNs, the proposal combined the LSTM model with the Gaussian Bayes model. While the approach in [77] combined the Genetic Algorithm with the MLP model (GA).

But all of the potential intrusion detection algorithms that were previously described need a lot of electricity. Therefore, in some additional experiments, the training process was moved from the WSN node to the console using Software Defined Network (SDN) technology [121]. As a result, these suggestions are rather effective in lowering the effort on WSN nodes. To transfer the training results to the sensors promptly, these approaches must change a number of protocols that take place between switches, controllers, and WSN nodes.

The authors of [122] provide distributed machine learning techniques for training intrusion detection switches and controllers in a hierarchical manner to minimize the impact of detection operations on terminal nodes. A decision tree, KNN, NB, and LR were used in the controller's first stage of training, and the switches were implemented in the second step of training. The research did not, however, go into detail about the enhancements and adjustments it made to the SDN protocols to support its recommendations. Additionally, in [123], the authors created an advanced intelligence framework by combining KNN with the arithmetic optimization algorithm (AOA) in evolutionary computing. Additionally, the authors in [124] employed SDN in the same context to enhance the detection of phishing assaults. The features extraction procedure, which was based on the URL and content of websites, was combined with conventional approaches (blacklist and whitelist) to create the optimization. Based on the results of the features extraction of packets that originate from users, the blacklist and whitelist are updated. The feature extraction procedure made use of the naive Bayes classifier. The controller then makes adjustments to the flow rule table before sending it to switches so they may take appropriate action for each packet that complies with the rules. The preceding method will be repeated if the message does not match any value in the rule action table. The suggested remedy is substantial and difficult, notwithstanding the advancements shown by their outcomes. The authors in [125] adopted a similar strategy by using machine learning based on neither stacking approaches to identify URL packets that are neither blacklisted nor whitelisted. Additionally, the authors in [126,127] combined CNN and SDN to increase the accuracy of URL detection. To categories a URL in a signature-based database to various phishing assaults, the CNN is employed in the controller. This categorization determines whether the incoming packet inspection is delivered immediately to the destination or enters slow mode. It will do additional inspections in the slow mode in order to update the signature-based database. Regardless of the financial viability of extracted features in decreasing instruction costs and enhancing effectiveness, none of the three took it into account in their plans.

2. Error Detection

Algorithms for ML are a good demonstration of detecting errors. Due to its many both software and hardware issues as well as their application in diverse disciplines, WSNs are therefore prone to errors and malfunctions. To rapidly find faults in a WSN, promising application methods must be used due to every one of these challenges. The trustworthy mechanisms ensemble learning approach was used by the authors in [23]. Four classification strategies—KNN, supervised learning, SVM, and continuous generating machine—are provided to increase the efficacy of the assumption component fusion technique. This approach does not, nevertheless, encapsulate the characteristics of unique WSN node breakdowns. This same researchers in [128] was using a hidden Markov model to predict the dynamics of transitions brought on by errors, and neural networks were used to categorise defects predicated upon that state transition produced by the Markov model. This allowed for the vibrant intercepting of the WSN nodes all through failure mortality rate. The authors thus concentrated on error detection and classification by combining a hidden Markov model with several neural networks, including actually training feature extraction, extreme learning machine, deterministic multilayer perceptron network, and rotational foundation function.

Regarding detecting errors in WSNs using standard ML techniques, the researchers in [129] employed Classification techniques, whereas the researchers in [130] were using the SVM estimation technique. In addition, the researchers of [131] proposed a continuous problem detection technique with real information streams employing iterative PCA and a cross Performers algorithm. The mistake in WSNs was found using the quick iterative principal component assessment technique. The SVDD classification was used to determine the different error categories. It is crucial to accomplish this since failing to identify a problem with the network of body sensors might lead to a wrong medical diagnosis. A Bayesian network-based technique for the wireless body area network's fault detection was disclosed in [24]. To use a Bayesian network approach, the temporal and territorial association of sensing devices was recorded. Sensor errors may be calculated using the proper threshold setting. Furthermore, utilising capacitors and WSN node metadata, the authors of [25] provided an error detection approach for identifying faulty WSN nodes. During the two-level validation of the proposal, the problematic nodes might be located. In the first step, an error inside the sensor node was identified using a Naive Bayesian classifier, and in the second stage, the misdiagnosis via the blockchain network or the gate was evaluated. This technique has a guaranteed average accuracy in numerical simulations. Additionally, [132] provided a flawed node placement and management technique for wireless connections based on ambiguous characteristics. The method's main objective was to utilize broken WSN nodes by showing the best pathways to the core network. It increases network lifespan and service dependability. A k-NN classification has indeed been utilised to differentiate these erroneous WSN nodes from either the regular Network elements depending on the abnormal sensor behaviour. The WSN network false positive rate is used by this modules to identify broken WSN nodes.

3. Congestion control

Although some people regard congestion management to be a component of the quality of the service, it may also be understood as part of the responsibilities that helps to ensure network availability. Furthermore, this field benefits greatly from machine learning methods.

Whenever a WSN node or information transfer gets additional data than it is capable handle, saturation develops in WSNs. Capacity is brought on by a variety of factors, including buffering node bypassing, message delivery competition, custom transmitting data schemes, particle conflict, variational shifting, and network throughput [27]. Energy use, packet loss, and edge latency are all impacted by the overcrowding [29]. By determining the best route and predicting network traffic, ML algorithms may assist with overcrowding management problems.

The researchers in [17] employed the Random Early Recognition efficient traffic management technique to identify congestion and assess the possibility of transmission errors. These method incorporates neural network and Percentage Integrating Diversification concept to decrease the queuing bottleneck and modify the network connectivity of each WSN node. The three mechanisms in the this method are bottleneck recognition, overcrowding notification, and data transmission change. Overload is initially identified using RED and flexible proportional plus integral

derivatives controller techniques. Indirect capacity notification is established when congestion is found. Finally, congestion is controlled by varying the transmission rate using a control scheme.

The developers of [133] also employed a proactive waiting line algorithm that detects overcrowding based on buffers saturation. Based on the size of the current queue, it determines the amount of network congestion and adjusts the queue length appropriately. In their suggestion, the relative integration differentiation control theory is used to WSN node queue management for the first time. The percentage, integral, and differential parameters of the relative integration differentiation controller are then configured using an online weight setting that is created utilising the neurons' capacity for self-learning and self-regulation. Finally, the control parameters of proportion, integral and differential parameters, and neuron learning rates are taken into account utilising the standard particle swarm optimization to neural relative integration differentiation approach in order to achieve an online optimization. In addition, the authors in [18] employed the fuzzy clustering approach in cluster nodes to tackle the congestion management issue when the cluster node buffer is full. This was done in the same context as employing fuzzy logic. This figure illustrates a two-tiered fuzzy logic system. Sensor nodes use ARIMA technology to try to predict the load profile, and fuzzy logic then chooses the nearest, least congested sensor node from among a pool of eligible mobile sensor nodes. The second fuzzy logic then uses the output of the first fuzzy logic to choose the proper nodes as cluster vertices, hence reducing network power consumption.

The authors of [19] suggested a heuristic method for locating the most effective optimum path based on learning Real-Time (A Star). The author concentrated on changing the topology and node degree. The data flow is then balanced using fuzzy logic to prevent congestion. If there is traffic, real-time learning is used to find an alternative, ideal way. Additionally, a rate-dependent congestion management mechanism based on cluster routing has been created [134] to lower energy consumption across the network. Reduced end-to-end latency and extended system life are two benefits of rate control technology. The first strategy for looking for cluster nodes uses a K-mean and greedy combination. The Firefly optimization technique, which is built for high packet delivery ratios, is then used to accomplish the rate control. Finally, the maximum throughput routing based on ant colony optimization is applied to deliver packets. To solve the congestion issue, the authors of [135] suggested a fuzzy sliding method congestion control strategy for WSNs. The signal-to-noise ratio of the wireless channel has been added to the TCP model in order to create a new cross-layer congestion management model between the transport layer and the data link layer. Then, a fuzzy sliding mode controller is developed by combining fuzzy control with sliding mode control. This controller significantly reduces the influence of unknown external disturbances while adaptively modifying the buffer queue length at busy nodes.

Authentication

The term "authentication" refers to a group of security measures that guarantee data came from the source and wasn't tampered with along the route [136]. Because of its strategy, active attacks like DoS and spoofing are neutralised. Both the network component and message characteristics are included in authentication. Entity authentication is accomplished because both the claimant and the verifier engage and communicate without providing any crucial information save the claim to be a certain entity. Message authentication would guarantee appropriateness even if it cannot confirm when a message was created. Conventional public-key encryption algorithms and techniques, like RSA [137], ECC [138], Diffie-Hellman [139], and others, are utilised in traditional networks for authentication [140]. The application of such processes, however, results in power depletion because of the features of wireless sensor networks that were previously addressed. It may be utilized in various works in addition to contemporary techniques of material and can provide information on accelerometers for users, but it also necessitates a powerful CPU and battery capacity. As a result, the subsystem authenticating method is an excellent choice for WSNs setups.

Through carrying out subsystem authenticating, ML algorithms may lower WSN power usage. Another core network system is the result that leverages LSTM to understand wireless equipment operations was proposed by authors in [141]. Their suggestion used the temporal connection between the wireless signals' I (preamble phase) and Q (quadrature phase) to identify reduced broadcasters from high-power rivals. Additionally, their findings demonstrated that deep learning algorithms are more accurate than conventional ML algorithms in comparison to other ML

techniques. The authors in [21] developed a deep learning-based physical layer authentication framework in the same context as physical layer authentication to increase the security of industrial WSNs. To make tagging the matching channel status information before transmission easier, a number of WSN nodes in diverse locations around the industrial environment have been found using application level authentication. Additionally, the authors of [22] authenticated WSN nodes using ML and radio channel data. The authors track the similarity of the radio channel between consecutive transmission intervals over a predetermined time (threshold) between authorized and unauthorized users. Additionally, the authors in [142] trace numerous physical layer properties based on a kernel-based ML method for adaptive authentication in a dynamic context. The recommended method reduces the authentication cost by modeling the physical layer authentication as a linear system, which reduces the authentication range from a concatenated N-dimensional feature vector to a single-dimensional (gradient) vector space. An adaptive algorithm based on kernel least-mean-square is proposed as an intelligent procedure for learning and tracking numerous attribute modifications, thereby improving the authentication efficiency. This is done by recasting the physical layer authentication learning (training) goal as a convex problem.

In [143-145], a new method based on the authentication interval log was suggested. To determine the authentication policy, the data collection (Access logs) is subjected to feature selection and machine learning techniques (KNN, RF, MLP, and gradient boosting). While [143] demonstrated the authentication accuracy and [145] shown how to leverage protocol access history to develop user authentication models, [144] only provided a tiny amount of information. These suggested solutions, however, only work provided the WSN nodes move frequently and continuously.

ML-Based WSN Diversified Security

The man in the middle, espionage, and selective forward are three domains outside of those covered in the preceding part where we explore the use of ML algorithms in wireless sensor network security.

The neural network technique, which has three neurons (devices, sensing, and delay) and five hidden neurons at three layers, was employed by the authors in [146]. The suggested technique keeps track of each node's health using those inputs to the network packets. A guy may have been present during the assault or there may have been incorrect information present if the results differ from the predicted value. The authors in [147] developed a new model to groups newly assigned devices in the home or workplace as trustworthy, strict, or limited in another method that use an ML algorithm to detect WSN devices. The device fingerprints created by the gateway are submitted to an IoT security service provider, who uses an ML classification model to identify the device based on its kind and traffic. The gateway is also in charge of monitoring the traffic produced by newly assigned devices. Additionally, the authors in [148] used an ML technique to separate WSN from non-WSN devices based on data flow. Sessions and attributes that were taken from each device were utilized for categorization.

A ML methodology was also utilized in the method described in [26] to assess if a benign node has changed to a malicious one. The employment of bio-inspiration as an immune mechanism to combat the impacts of malicious nodes is also possible. The data are first split into two groups by the k-means algorithm: normal and defective. Next, a decision block containing three regions—normal, defect, and critical at the borders—is generated using SVM. An anomaly detection method is used to calculate the mean and standard deviation of the WSN node provided by the SVM dataset. After an abnormality is found, the immune system is activated. Similar to biological processes, virtual antibodies are produced, and malicious nodes are ultimately eliminated.

The authors in [149] assessed ML interference detection algorithms that just analyze samples received in-phase (I) and quadratic phase with regard to WSN privacy and safety (Q). Once an intrusion has been discovered, mitigation measures may be applied, emphasizing the importance of interference detection. Because the Random Forest classifier consists of a large number of distinct decision trees that cooperate as an ensemble, it was selected. The effectiveness of Random Forest and SVM classifiers for WSN channel identification was then examined by the same authors in [74]. The authors gathered additional data from wired devices after extracting data characteristics from the samples they got in I and Q. The authors then use the information gathered from I and Q to train ML algorithms, test them in signal-free, valid signal, and jamming signal scenarios. The results of these classifiers were then compared to the information gathered from wires.

CONVERSATION AND UNRESOLVED PROBLEMS

Every recommendation in the preceding section has the potential to enhance one maybe more steps in the remote monitoring procedure for WSNs. The research under examination offered useful details concerning the variations in ML techniques' outcomes and how they are implemented. Additionally, the Techniques in several protection need areas, including dependability, produce astounding results by tracking mistakes, bottlenecks, and spotting attack traffic. Additionally, Techniques produced excellent results when used to offer authenticity utilizing the network topology and analyze the information flow. There is still a hole, unfortunately, at which Techniques are incapable of meet all of the safety needs in WSN. Consequently, the ML algorithms employed and associated techniques must adhere to the standards established by government security organizations.

The outcomes of the statistical study on WSN security mechanisms that was carried out on the examined Learning algorithms are shown in Figure 12. The study displays the various security measures utilized in WSNs together with the proportion of ML algorithms used in each measure.

Figure 12 shows how 41% of the papers that were analyzed employed ML algorithms for vulnerability scanning. In terms of mistake detection, 18% comes in second. The remaining 14% congregate for further research. This is because ML algorithms are expensive to implement on devices and need training procedures. Additionally, the majority of it was used to preserve network availability, and its application to both secrecy and integrity was challenging. The application of ML techniques in the protection of WSNs of three categories are covered in the following sections, along with certain unresolved concerns that still need in-depth investigation. We also provide potential solutions to these concerns.

Figure 12. Shows the Statistical Analysis for the WSN Protection ML Techniques

Position of the ML Training Phase

Given that it is decentralized rather than centralized and that all of its embedded devices have the same CPU and energy requirements, among the most crucial concerns for this kind of system is where should deploy ML in the instructional procedure. Therefore, we find uncertainty regarding how such approaches were applied in various WSN contexts in the majority of research that have employed ML methodologies. The majority of recent research [77,78,120] have increased the accuracy of detecting attacks or malicious nodes, however it is unclear how to train these algorithms. We are also unaware of the power consumption these embedded devices incur while doing training operations for DoS monitoring.

Through executing management and transmitting their outcomes to the WSN node [124,126], other writers have benefited [150]. Although it is regarded as a profitable and wonderful concept, it also requires creating unique methods to handle these elements. Networks become programmable thanks to technologies enabling quicker service administration and versatility in data upgrading.

Using the same technology, this solution separates customer network into a collection of tiny networks with autonomous administration and connections to nearby networks [153].

Figure 13. Shows the SDN Architecture Used for WSN-Based ML Algorithms

A device known as an External storage, which is in charge of controlling both the network's hardware and all of its users, is in charge of administering small networks, which are likewise centralized in administration. So, if we assume that all network sensors are members of the same SDN, as illustrated in Figure 13, then. It becomes feasible to move the data training operations for ML techniques from of the Network nodes. We will do this while providing free ongoing security updates for the WSN. For instance, [127] has already made this move, although SDN-Switch still need a number of changes to prevent packet congestion during inspections.

Figure 13 shows that the SDN is made up of a centralized technology. External storage use the AP to communicate to wireless devices. These devices communicate with one another using the OpenFlow protocol [154]. It transferring data between the switches and routers and the controller. The issue regarding where to train algorithmic ML therefore well addressed by this concept. In addition, other unresolved concerns, such as the equality of assignments and types of labour across all Network elements in this kind of network, might be exploited. Therefore, creating a grouping concept amongst close-by WSNs to coordinate the development of Statistical models is another option. ML algorithms are dealt with by creating specific protocols for delivering and receiving input in addition to outcomes.

Compact Machine Learning Approaches

Additionally, we have seen that a team of writers has constructed sophisticated ML algorithms without considering the necessary hardware in order to increase efficiency and accuracy. Additionally, as was already said, ML algorithms fall into several categories, and they are supported by algorithms that speed up training and improve accuracy. As a result, it is feasible to develop a hybrid type (ML method) that is portable and appropriate for use with these kinds of embedded devices. The capacity of WSN nodes to differentiate between different ML methods and autonomously choose the best one based on many criteria, such as the kind of data, the amount of data, and the available power, may, on the other hand, be developed. Additionally, this is one of the unresolved problems that scholars should work to resolve in the future.

In addition, neither reinforcement learning [155] nor transfer learning [156] were discussed in any of the research examined in the domains of use of ML to assist the security of WSNs. These

technologies are often used in the development of ML. Intermediate product is based on which was before algorithms, while back propagation involves knowledge learning rather than data-based training. Therefore, both approaches may be tried in open problems together with SDN.

Privacy Issues

As was already indicated, all WSN terminals have the same amounts of CPU, resource, and jobs. The surroundings in whom these embedding technologies function are likewise mobile, therefore there is ongoing change in the interaction here between node's communications and its peers. With all of these changes, the node's present authentication system is ineffective. Additionally, whatever the researchers did to aid in the verification process by leveraging the physical layer and employing ML techniques is a smart choice that minimises synchronisation and acknowledgement in addition to saves nodes resources. The confidentiality situation is one of the issues that are still up for debate. It is open to explore how to prevent competitors from inadvertently or purposefully breaching the confidentiality of detectors.

Trust Domain

The growth of trust between WSN nodes is one of the problems that might improve the security of these networks [157]. This may also be achieved by watching a WSN node's activity and, using ML algorithms, designating the trusted label "Reliable" to nodes that have a solid reputation among their neighbours. This is done by enhancing WSN management so that each node's behaviour can be examined, and the findings can then be shared with other nodes. Together with the SD-Controller, ML algorithms will be crucial in examining the behaviour of nearby nodes.

CONCLUSION

In a variety of situations, the wireless sensor network is designed to perform commonplace activities including data gathering and monitoring. Due to its ease of use, capacity for specialised tasks, and cheap cost, this kind of network has come to be more reliant on the Internet of Things. The problem of security is one of several that have arisen as a result of the expanding proliferation. Fundamental security requirements in wireless sensor networks are more challenging to provide than in conventional networks because of CPU and power constraints. Therefore, creative solutions to this issue are needed. Numerous researches have used ML approaches in an effort to address this issue. It is also challenging to adapt ML algorithms to WSNs. In this article, we offered a case study that served as an illustration of the wireless sensor network architecture, as well as the environment, applications, operational procedure, and security issues that it raises. Then we looked at the ML algorithms that were used in them, and we did an analytical examination of the most current research that attempted to apply ML algorithms to increase security in WSNs. We also highlighted each study's benefits and drawbacks. Because machine learning algorithms have a bright future in the realm of security for WSNs, this article focused on demonstrating potential future solutions that might aid in using them.

Intrusion detection and error detection are the most often used ML algorithms in the security of WSNs, according to statistical data. Using SDN technology is one of the most important and effective options for extending the use of ML algorithms in other security areas. It may be used to decrease utilization costs while increasing WSN node efficiency.

CONTRIBUTIONS FROM ALL AUTHORS

This work was written by all authors. Writing—original draught, T.A.-A. and R.W.; visualisation, R.A.; supervision, R.A.; writing—review and editing, R.A., R.W. and T.A.-A.; revision and correction, R.A.; investigation, R.A. and T.A.-A.; data duration, R.A. and R.W. The manuscript's published form was approved by all authors once they had read it.

FUNDING

There was no any grant or funding for this research paper.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors say they have none.

REFERENCES

1. R. Wazirali, R. Ahmad, A. Al-Amayreh, M. Al-Madi, A. Khalifeh, "Secure Watermarking Schemes and Their Approaches in the IoT Technology: An Overview," *Electronics*, vol. 10, id. 1744, 2021. DOI: [10.3390/electronics10141744](https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10141744)
2. M. Bouaziz, A. Rachedi, "A survey on mobility management protocols in Wireless Sensor Networks based on 6LoWPAN technology," *Comput. Commun.*, vol. 74, pp. 3–15, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/j.comcom.2014.10.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comcom.2014.10.004)
3. H.A.A. Al-Kashoash, H. Kharrufa, Y. Al-Nidawi, A.H. Kemp, "Congestion control in wireless sensor and 6LoWPAN networks: Toward the Internet of Things," *Wirel. Networks*, vol. 25, pp. 4493–4522, 2019. DOI: [10.1007/s11276-018-1743-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11276-018-1743-y)
4. M.A. Moridi, Y. Kawamura, M. Sharifzadeh, E.K. Chanda, M. Wagner, H. Okawa, "Performance analysis of ZigBee network topologies for underground space monitoring and communication systems," *Tunn.Undergr. Sp. Technol.*, vol. 71, pp. 201–209, 2008. DOI: [10.1016/j.tust.2017.08.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2017.08.018)
5. M.A. Ertürk, M.A. Aydın, M.T. Büyükakkas, H. Evirgen, "A Survey on LoRaWAN Architecture, Protocol and Technologies," *Futur.Internet*, vol. 11, id. 216, 2019. DOI: [10.3390/fi11100216](https://doi.org/10.3390/fi11100216)
6. V. Kumar, S. Tiwari, "Routing in IPv6 over low-power wireless personal area networks (6LoWPAN): A survey," *J. Comput. Netw. Commun.*, vol. 2012, id. 316839, 2012. DOI: [10.1155/2012/316839](https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/316839)
7. K.A. Darabkh, M.Z. El-Yabroudi, A.H. El-Mousa, "BPA-CRP: A Balanced Power-Aware Clustering and Routing Protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks," Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier, 2019.
8. D.K. Sah, T. Amgoth, "Parametric survey on cross-layer designs for wireless sensor networks," *Comput. Sci. Rev.*, vol. 27, pp. 112–134, 2018. DOI: [10.1016/j.cosrev.2017.12.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2017.12.002)
9. O.A. Khashan, R. Ahmad, N.M. Khafajah, "An automated lightweight encryption scheme for secure and energy-efficient communication in wireless sensor networks," *Ad.Hoc.Netw.*, vol. 115, id. 102448. DOI: [10.1016/j.adhoc.2021.102448](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2021.102448)
10. R. Ahmad, E.A. Sundararajan, T. Abu-Ain, Analysis the Effect of Clustering and Lightweight Encryption Approaches on WSNs Lifetime. In Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics (ICEEI), Kuala Terengganu, Malaysia, 12–13 October 2021; IEEE: Selangor, Malaysia, pp. 1–6, 2021.
11. M.S. Yousefpoor, H. Barati, "Dynamic key management algorithms in wireless sensor networks: A survey," *Comput. Commun.* vol. 134, pp. 52–69, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.comcom.2018.11.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comcom.2018.11.005)
12. M. Rana, Q. Mamun, R. Islam, "Lightweight cryptography in IoT networks: A survey," *Futur.Gener.Comput. Syst.*, vol. 129, pp. 77–89, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.future.2021.11.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2021.11.011)
13. H. Sharma, A. Haque, F. Blaabjerg, "Machine learning in wireless sensor networks for smart cities: A survey," *Electronics*, vol. 10, id. 1012, 2021. DOI: [10.3390/electronics10091012](https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10091012)
14. S. Schwendemann, Z. Amjad, A. Sikora, "A survey of machine-learning techniques for condition monitoring and predictive maintenance of bearings in grinding machines," *Comput.Ind.*, vol. 125, id. 103380, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.compind.2020.103380](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2020.103380)
15. H. Liu, B. Lang, "Machine learning and deep learning methods for intrusion detection systems: A survey," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 9, id. 4396, 2019. DOI: [10.3390/app9204396](https://doi.org/10.3390/app9204396)

16. L. Cui, S. Yang, F. Chen, Z. Ming, N. Lu, J. Qin, "A survey on application of machine learning for Internet of Things," *Int. J. Mach. Learn. Cybern.*, vol. 9, pp.1399–1417, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/s13042-018-0834-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13042-018-0834-5)
17. A.A. Rezaee, F. Pasandideh, "A Fuzzy Congestion Control Protocol Based on Active Queue Management in Wireless Sensor Networks with Medical Applications," *Wirel. Pers. Commun.*, vol. 98, pp. 815–842, 2018. DOI: [10.1080/03772063.2024.2310123](https://doi.org/10.1080/03772063.2024.2310123)
18. M. Masdari, *Energy Efficient Clustering and Congestion Control in WSNs with Mobile Sinks*. Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2020.
19. G. Sangeetha, M. Vijayalakshmi, S. Ganapathy, A. Kannan, "A heuristic path search for congestion control in WSN," *Lect. Notes Netw. Syst.*, vol. 11, pp. 485–495, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/978-981-10-3953-9_47](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3953-9_47)
20. S. Chen, H. Wen, J. Wu, J. Chen, W. Liu, L. Hu, Y. Chen, "Physical-Layer Channel Authentication for 5G via Machine Learning Algorithm," *Wirel. Commun. Mob. Comput.*, vol. 2018, id. 6039878, 2018. DOI: [10.1155/2018/6039878](https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/6039878)
21. R.F. Liao, H. Wen, J. Wu, F. Pan, A. Xu, Y. Jiang, F. Xie, M. Cao, "Deep-learning-based physical layer authentication for industrial wireless sensor networks," *Sensors*, vol. 19, id. 2440, 2019. DOI: [10.3390/s19112440](https://doi.org/10.3390/s19112440)
22. F. Pan, H. Wen, R. Liao, Y. Jiang, A. Xu, K. Ouyang, X. Zhu, "Physical layer authentication based on channel information and machine learning," in Proceedings of the 2017 IEEE Conference on Communications and Network Security (CNS), Las Vegas, NV, USA, 9–11 October 2017, vol. 40, pp. 364–365, 2017. DOI: [10.1109/CNS.2017.8228614](https://doi.org/10.1109/CNS.2017.8228614)
23. A. Javaid, N. Javaid, Z. Wadud, T. Saba, O.E. Sheta, M.Q. Saleem, M.E. Alzahrani, "Machine learning algorithms and fault detection for improved belief function based decision fusion in wireless sensor networks," *Sensors*, vol. 19, id. 1334, 2019. DOI: [10.3390/s19061334](https://doi.org/10.3390/s19061334)
24. H. Zhang, J. Liu, N. Kato, "Threshold Tuning-Based Wearable Sensor Fault Detection for Reliable Medical Monitoring Using Bayesian Network Model," *IEEE Syst. J.*, vol. 12, pp. 1886–1896, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/JSYST.2016.2600582](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2016.2600582)
25. C. Titouna, M. Aliouat, M. Gueroui, "FDS: Fault Detection Scheme for Wireless Sensor Networks," *Wirel. Pers. Commun.*, vol. 86, pp. 549–562, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/s11277-015-2944-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-015-2944-7)
26. H. Rathore, V. Badarla, S. Jha, A. Gupta, "Novel approach for security in Wireless Sensor Network using bio-inspirations," in Proceedings of the 2014 Sixth International Conference on Communication Systems and Networks (COMSNETS), Bangalore, India, 6–10 January 2014, 2014. DOI: [10.1109/COMSNETS.2014.6734875](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMSNETS.2014.6734875)
27. D. Praveen Kumar, T. Amgoth, C.S.R. Annavarapu, "Machine learning algorithms for wireless sensor networks: A survey," *Inf. Fusion*, vol. 49, pp. 1–25, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.inffus.2018.09.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2018.09.013)
28. M.N.U. Islam, A. Fahmin, M.S. Hossain, M. Atiquzzaman, "Denial-of-Service Attacks on Wireless Sensor Network and Defense Techniques. Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2021.
29. A. Bohloulzadeh, M. Rajaei, "A Survey on Congestion Control Protocols in Wireless Sensor Networks," *Int. J. Wirel. Inf. Networks*, vol. 27, pp. 365–384, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s10776-020-00479-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10776-020-00479-3)
30. R. Vinayakumar, M. Alazab, K.P Soman, P. Poornachandran, A. Al-Nemrat, S. Venkatraman, "Deep Learning Approach for Intelligent Intrusion Detection System," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 41525–41550, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2895334](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2895334)
31. S.T. Patel, N.H. Mistry, "A review: Sybil attack detection techniques in WSN" in Proceedings of the 2017 4th International Conference on Electronics and Communication Systems (ICECS), Coimbatore, India, 24–25 February 2017; Volume 17, pp. 184–188, 2017.
32. J.Y. Yu, E. Lee, S.R. Oh, Y.D. Seo, Y.G. Kim, "A Survey on Security Requirements for WSNs: Focusing on the Characteristics Related to Security," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 45304–45324, 2020. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2977778](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2977778)

33. M. Al-Emran, S.I. Malik, M.N. Al-Kabi, "A Survey of Internet of Things (IoT) in Education: Opportunities and Challenges. In Toward Social Internet of Things (SIoT): Enabling Technologies, Architectures and Applications. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2020.
34. G. Zhang, L. Kou, L. Zhang, C. Liu, Q. Da, J. Sun, "A New Digital Watermarking Method for Data Integrity Protection in the Perception Layer of IoT," *Secur.Commun.Netw.*, vol. 2017, id. 3126010, 2017. DOI: [10.1155/2017/3126010](https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/3126010)
35. L. Yi, X. Tong, Z. Wang, M. Zhang, H. Zhu, J. Liu, "A novel block encryption algorithm based on chaotic S-Box for wireless sensor network," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 53079–53090, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2911395](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2911395)
36. N.R. Patel, S. Kumar, Wireless Sensor Networks' Challenges and Future Prospects. In Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on System Modeling & Advancement in Research Trends (SMART), Moradabad, India, 23–24 November 2018; pp. 60–65, 2018.
37. X. Zhang, H.M. Heys, C. Li, "Energy efficiency of encryption schemes applied to wireless sensor networks," *Secur.Commun.Netw.*, vol. 5, pp. 789–808, 2012. DOI: [10.1002/sec.375](https://doi.org/10.1002/sec.375)
38. J. Luo, Z. Zhang, C. Liu, H. Luo, "Reliable and Cooperative Target Tracking Based on WSN and WiFi in Indoor Wireless Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 24846–24855, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2830762](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2830762)
39. B. Qiao, K. Ma, "An enhancement of the ZigBee wireless sensor network using bluetooth for industrial field measurement," in Proceedings of the 2015 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Workshop Series on Advanced Materials and Processes for RF and THz Applications (IMWS-AMP), Suzhou, China, 1–3 July 2015; pp. 2–4, 2015.
40. R.K. Ghosh, Wireless Networking and Mobile Data Management, Singapore: Springer, 2017.
41. Y. Yang, L. Wu, G. Yin, L. Li, H. Zhao, "A Survey on Security and Privacy Issues in Internet-of-Things," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 4, pp. 1250–1258, 2017. DOI: [10.1109/JIOT.2017.2694844](https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2017.2694844)
42. S. Sicari, A. Rizzardi, L.A. Grieco, A. Coen-Portisini, "Security, privacy and trust in Internet of Things: The road ahead," *Comput.Netw.*, vol. 76, pp. 146–164, 2015. DOI: [10.1016/j.comnet.2014.11.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2014.11.008)
43. F. Akhtar, M.H. Rehmani, "Energy replenishment using renewable and traditional energy resources for sustainable wireless sensor networks: A review. Renew," *Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 45, pp. 769–784, 2015. DOI: [10.1016/j.rser.2015.02.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.02.021)
44. C.C. Lee, "Security and privacy in wireless sensor networks: Advances and challenges," *Sensors*, vol. 20, id. 744, 2020. DOI: [10.3390/s20030744](https://doi.org/10.3390/s20030744)
45. M. Winkler, M. Street, K.-D. Tuchs, K. Wrona, Wireless Sensor Networks for Military Purposes. In Autonomous Sensor Networks, Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2012.
46. J. Pan, Z. Xu, S. Li, "Security mechanism for a wireless-sensor-network-based healthcare monitoring system," *IET Commun.*, vol. 6, pp. 3274–3280. 2012. DOI: [10.3390/s20030744](https://doi.org/10.3390/s20030744)
47. E. CalvaneseStrinati, S. Barbarossa, J.L. Gonzalez-Jimenez, D. Ktenas, N. Cassiau, L. Maret, C. Dehos, "6G: The Next Frontier: From Holographic Messaging to Artificial Intelligence Using Subterahertz and Visible Light Communication," *IEEE Veh. Technol. Mag.*, vol. 14, pp. 42–50, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/MVT.2019.2921162](https://doi.org/10.1109/MVT.2019.2921162)
48. H. Wang, J. Wang, M. Huang, "Building a smart home system with WSN and service robot," in Proceedings of the 2013 Fifth International Conference on Measuring Technology and Mechatronics Automation, Hong Kong, China, 16–17 January 2013; pp. 353–356, 2013. DOI: [10.1109/ICMTMA.2013.90](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMTMA.2013.90)
49. N.B.H. Kasah, A.H.B.M. Aman, Z.S.M. Attarbashi, Y. Fazea, "Investigation on 6LoWPAN data security for internet of things," in Proceedings of the 2020 2nd International Conference on Computer and Information Sciences, ICCIS 2020, Aljouf, KSA, Saudi Arabia, 7–9 April 2020; Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2020. DOI: [10.1109/ICCIS49240.2020.9257661](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIS49240.2020.9257661)

50. M. Seliem, K. Elgazzar, "IoTeWay: A Secure Framework Architecture for 6LoWPAN Based IoT Applications," in Proceedings of the 2018 IEEE Global Conference on Internet of Things (GCIoT 2018), Alexandria, Egypt, 5–7 December 2018; pp. 1–5, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/GCIoT.2018.8620137](https://doi.org/10.1109/GCIoT.2018.8620137)
51. S. Messaoud, A. Bradai, S.H.R. Bukhari, P.T.A. Quang, O. Ben Ahmed, M. Atri, "A survey on machine learning in Internet of Things: Algorithms, strategies, and applications," *Internet Things*, vol. 12, id. 100314, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.iot.2020.100314](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iot.2020.100314)
52. J. Mo, H. Chen, "A Lightweight Secure User Authentication and Key Agreement Protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks," *Secur. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 2019, id. 2136506, 2019. DOI: [10.1155/2019/2136506](https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/2136506)
53. A. Nelli, S. Mangasuli, "Wireless Sensor Networks: An Overview on Security Issues and Challenges," *Int. J. Adv. Eng. Manag. Sci.*, vol. 3, pp. 209–214, 2017.
54. A.G. Finogeev, A.A. Finogeev, "Information attacks and security in wireless sensor networks of industrial SCADA systems," *ACM Int. Conf. Proc. Ser.*, vol. 5, pp. 6–16, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/J.JII.2017.02.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JII.2017.02.002)
55. B. Yang, F. Liu, L. Yuan, Y. Zhang, "6LoWPAN Protocol Based Infrared Sensor Network Human Target Locating System," in Proceedings of the Proceedings of the 15th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications, ICIEA 2020, Kristiansand, Norway, 9–13 November 2020; pp. 1773–1779, 2020. DOI: [10.1109/ICIEA48937.2020.9248292](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEA48937.2020.9248292)
56. M. Wang, Y. Lu, J. Qin, "A dynamic MLP-based DDoS attack detection method using feature selection and feedback," *Comput. Secur.*, vol. 88, id. 101645, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.cose.2019.101645](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2019.101645)
57. P.M. Kumar, U.D. Gandhi, "Enhanced DTLS with CoAP-based authentication scheme for the internet of things in healthcare application," *J. Supercomput.*, vol. 76, pp. 3963–3983, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11227-017-2169-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-017-2169-5)
58. J. Olsson, 6LoWPAN Demystified, Dallas, TX, USA: Texas Instruments, 2014.
59. Y. Yang, X. Zheng, W. Guo, X. Liu, V. Chang, "Privacy-preserving smart IoT-based healthcare big data storage and self-adaptive access control system," *Inf. Sci.*, vol. 479, pp. 567–592, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.ins.2018.02.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2018.02.005)
60. R.H. Ahmad, A.S.K. Pathan, "A Study on M2M (Machine to Machine) System and Communication," in Security Solutions and Applied Cryptography in Smart Grid Communications; IGI Global: Hershey, PA, USA, 2016.
61. G. Glissa, A. Meddeb, "6LoWPAN multi-layered security protocol based on IEEE 802.15.4 security features," in Proceedings of the 2017 13th International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC), Valencia, Spain, 26–30 June 2017; pp. 264–269, 2017. DOI: [10.1016/j.adhoc.2018.01.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2018.01.013)
62. M. Mamdouh, M.A.I. Elrukhsi, A. Khattab, "Securing the Internet of Things and Wireless Sensor Networks via Machine Learning: A Survey," in Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Computer and Applications (ICCA), Beirut, Lebanon, 25–26 August 2018; pp. 215–218, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/COMAPP.2018.8460440](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMAPP.2018.8460440)
63. A. Karakaya, S. Akleyek, "A survey on security threats and authentication approaches in wireless sensor networks," in Proceedings of the 2018 6th International Symposium on Digital Forensic and Security (ISDFS), Antalya, Turkey, 22–25 March 2018; pp. 1–4, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/ISDFS.2018.8355381](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISDFS.2018.8355381)
64. Y. Zou, G. Wang, "Intercept Behavior Analysis of Industrial Wireless Sensor Networks in the Presence of Eavesdropping Attack," *Proc. IEEE Trans. Ind. Inform.*, vol. 12, pp. 780–787, 2016. DOI: [10.1109/TII.2015.2399691](https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2015.2399691)
65. T. Hamza, G. Kaddoum, A. Meddeb, G. Matar, "A survey on intelligent MAC layer jamming attacks and countermeasures in wsns," in Proceedings of the 2016 IEEE 84th Vehicular Technology

- Conference (VTC-Fall), Montreal, QC, Canada, 18–21 September 2016; pp. 42–56, 2016. DOI: [10.1109/SURV.2009.090404](https://doi.org/10.1109/SURV.2009.090404)
66. P. Reindl, K. Nygard, X. Du, “Defending malicious collision attacks in wireless sensor networks,” in Proceedings of the 2010 IEEE/IFIP International Conference on Embedded and Ubiquitous Computing, Hong Kong, China, 11–13 December 2010; pp. 771–776, 2010. DOI: [10.1109/EUC.2010.121](https://doi.org/10.1109/EUC.2010.121)
67. A. Tayebi, S.M. Berber, A. Swain, “Wireless sensor network attacks: An overview and critical analysis with detailed investigation on jamming attack effects,” *Smart Sens. Meas. Instrum.*, vol. 11, pp. 201–221, 2015. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-10948-0_10](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10948-0_10)
68. J.R. Ward, M. Younis, “A cross-layer defense scheme for countering traffic analysis attacks in Wireless Sensor Networks,” in Proceedings of the MILCOM—2016 IEEE Military Communications Conference, Baltimore, MD, USA, 1–3 November 2016; pp. 972–977, 2016. DOI: [10.1109/MILCOM.2015.7357571](https://doi.org/10.1109/MILCOM.2015.7357571)
69. A.B. Karuppiah, J. Dalfiah, K. Yuvashri, S. Rajaram, “An improvised hierarchical black hole detection algorithm in Wireless Sensor Networks,” in Proceedings of the International Conference on Innovation Information in Computing Technologies, Chennai, India, 19–20 February 2015; pp. 1–7, 2015. DOI: [10.1109/ICIICT.2015.7396103](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIICT.2015.7396103)
70. N.M. Alajmi, K.M. Elleithy, “Selective forwarding detection (SFD) in wireless sensor networks,” in Proceedings of the 2015 Long Island Systems, Applications and Technology, Farmingdale, NY, USA, 1 May 2015. DOI: [10.1109/LISAT.2015.7160207](https://doi.org/10.1109/LISAT.2015.7160207)
71. H. Modares, R. Salleh, A. Moravejosharieh, “Overview of security issues in wireless sensor networks,” in Proceedings of the 2011 Third International Conference on Computational Intelligence, Modelling & Simulation, Langkawi, Malaysia, 20–22 September 2011; pp. 308–311, 2011. DOI: [10.1109/CIMSim.2011.62](https://doi.org/10.1109/CIMSim.2011.62)
72. A. Kumar, T.J. Lim, “EDIMA: Early Detection of IoT Malware Network Activity Using Machine Learning Techniques,” in Proceedings of the 2019 IEEE 5th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT), Limerick, Ireland, 15–18 April 2019; pp. 289–294, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/WF-IoT.2019.8767194](https://doi.org/10.1109/WF-IoT.2019.8767194)
73. M. Shen, X. Tang, L. Zhu, X. Du, M. Guizani, “Privacy-Preserving Support Vector Machine Training over Blockchain-Based Encrypted IoT Data in Smart Cities,” *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 6, pp. 7702–7712, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/JIOT.2019.2901840](https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2019.2901840)
74. G.D. O’Mahony, P.J. Harris, C.C. Murphy, “Investigating Supervised Machine Learning Techniques for Channel Identification in Wireless Sensor Networks,” in Proceedings of the 2020 31st Irish Signals and Systems Conference (ISSC), Letterkenny, Ireland, 11–12 June 2020. DOI: [10.1109/ISSC49989.2020.9180209](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISSC49989.2020.9180209)
75. G.M. Borkar, L.H. Patil, D. Dalgade, A. Hutke, “A novel clustering approach and adaptive SVM classifier for intrusion detection in WSN: A data mining concept,” *Sustain. Comput. Inform. Syst.*, vol. 23, pp. 120–135, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/J.SUSCOM.2019.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SUSCOM.2019.06.002)
76. M. Premkumar, T.V.P. Sundararajan, “DLDM: Deep learning-based defense mechanism for denial of service attacks in wireless sensor networks,” *Microprocess. Microsyst.*, vol. 79, id. 103278, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.micpro.2020.103278](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpro.2020.103278)
77. K.J. Singh, T. De, “MLP-GA based algorithm to detect application layer DDoS attack,” *J. Inf. Secur. Appl.*, vol. 36, pp. 145–153, 2017. DOI: [10.1016/j.jisa.2017.09.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisa.2017.09.004)
78. X. Lu, D. Han, L. Duan, Q. Tian, “Intrusion detection of wireless sensor networks based on IPSO algorithm and BP neural network,” *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 22, pp. 221–232, 2020. DOI: [10.1504/IJCSE.2020.107344](https://doi.org/10.1504/IJCSE.2020.107344)
79. M. Abuhamad, T. Abuhmed, D. Mohaisen, D. Nyang, “AUToSen: Deep-learning-based implicit continuous authentication using smartphone sensors,” *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 7, pp. 5008–5020, 2020. DOI: [10.1109/JIOT.2020.2975779](https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.2975779)

80. S. Modak, D. Sehgal, J. Valadi, "Applications of artificial intelligence and machine learning in viral biology," *Glob. Virol. III Virol. 21st Century*, vol. 154, pp. 1–39, 2019. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-29022-1_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-29022-1_1)
81. G. Vashisht, *ML Algorithms for Smart Sensor Networks*. In *Smart Sensor Networks*; Cham, Switzerland: Springer, pp. 73–103, 2021.
82. M. Ali, L.T. Jung, A.H. Abdel-Aty, M.Y. Abubakar, M. Elhoseny, I. Ali, "Semantic-k-NN algorithm: An enhanced version of traditional k-NN algorithm," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 151, id. 113374, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113374](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113374)
83. I.H. Sarker, A. Colman, J. Han, A.I. Khan, Y.B. Abushark, K. Salah, "BehavDT: A Behavioral Decision Tree Learning to Build User-Centric Context-Aware Predictive Model," *Mob. Netw. Appl.*, vol. 25, pp. 1151–1161, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11036-019-01443-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11036-019-01443-z)
84. R.F. Bikmukhamedov, A.F. Nadeev, "Lightweight machine learning classifiers of IoT traffic flows," in *Proceedings of the 2019 Systems of Signal Synchronization, Generating and Processing in Telecommunications (SYNCHROINFO)*, Yaroslavl, Russia, 1–3 July 2019. DOI: [10.1109/SYNCHROINFO.2019.8814156](https://doi.org/10.1109/SYNCHROINFO.2019.8814156)
85. A. Sekulic', M. Kilibarda, G.B.M. Heuvelink, M. Nikolic', B. Bajat, "Random Forest Spatial Interpolation," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 12, id.1687, 2020. DOI: [10.3390/rs12101687](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12101687)
86. D.A. Pisner, D.M. Schnyer, Support vector machine, in "Machine Learning", Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier pp. 101–121, 2020.
87. T. Li, J. Li, Z. Liu, P. Li, C. Jia, "Differentially private Naive Bayes learning over multiple data sources," *Inf. Sci.*, vol. 444, pp. 89–104, 2018. DOI: [10.1016/j.ins.2018.02.056](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2018.02.056)
88. C.H. Lee, "An information-theoretic filter approach for value weighted classification learning in naive Bayes," *Data Knowl. Eng.*, vol. 113, pp. 116–128, 2018. DOI: [10.1016/j.datak.2017.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.datak.2017.11.002)
89. M. Yaghini, M.M. Khoshraftar, M. Fallahi, "A hybrid algorithm for artificial neural network training," *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 26, pp. 293–301, 2013. DOI: [10.1016/j.engappai.2012.01.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2012.01.023)
90. C.Y.J. Peng, K.L. Lee, G.M. Ingersoll, "An introduction to logistic regression analysis and reporting," *J. Educ. Res.*, vol. 96, pp. 3–14, 2002. DOI: [10.1080/00220670209598786](https://doi.org/10.1080/00220670209598786)
91. W. Liu, P.P. Pokharel, J.C. Principe, "The Kernel Least-Mean-Square Algorithm," *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 56, pp. 543–554, 2008. DOI: [10.1109/TSP.2007.907881](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2007.907881)
92. Z. Ghahramani, "Unsupervised Learning. In *Summer School on Machine Learning*, Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, pp. 72–112, 2004.
93. K.P. Sinaga, M. Yang, "Unsupervised K-Means Clustering Algorithm," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 80716–80727, 2020. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2988796](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2988796)
94. S. Kambalimath, P.C. Deka, "A basic review of fuzzy logic applications in hydrology and water resources," *Appl. Water Sci.*, vol. 10, id. 191, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s13201-020-01276-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-020-01276-2)
95. A.H. Marblestone, G. Wayne, K.P. Kording, "Toward an integration of deep learning and neuroscience," *Front. Comput. Neurosci.*, vol. 10, pp. 1–41, 2016. DOI: [10.3389/fncom.2016.00094](https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2016.00094)
96. R. Wazirali, R. Ahmed, "Hybrid Feature Extractions and CNN for Enhanced Periocular Identification During COVID-19," *Comput. Syst. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 41, pp. 305–320, 2022. DOI: [10.32604/csse.2022.020504](https://doi.org/10.32604/csse.2022.020504)
97. S. Albawi, T.A. Mohammed, S. Al-Zawi, "Understanding of a convolutional neural network," in *Proceedings of the 2017 International Conference on Engineering and Technology (ICET)*, Antalya, Turkey, 21–23 August 2017; pp. 1–6, 2017. DOI: [10.1109/ICEngTechnol.2017.8308186](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEngTechnol.2017.8308186)
98. T. Kim, L.F. Vecchietti, K. Choi, S. Lee, D. Har, "Machine Learning for Advanced Wireless Sensor Networks: A Review," *IEEE Sens. J.*, vol. 21, pp. 12379–12397, 2021. DOI: [10.1109/JSEN.2020.3035846](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3035846)

99. A. Sherstinsky, "Fundamentals of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network," *Phys. D Nonlinear Phenom.*, vol. 404, id. 132306, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.physd.2019.132306](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physd.2019.132306)
100. K. Greff, R.K. Srivastava, J. Koutnik, B.R. Steunebrink, J. Schmidhuber, "LSTM: A Search Space Odyssey," *IEEE Trans. Neural Networks Learn. Syst.*, vol. 28, pp. 2222–2232, 2017. DOI: [10.1109/tnnls.2016.2582924](https://doi.org/10.1109/tnnls.2016.2582924)
101. X. Sun, J. Xu, C. Jiang, J. Feng, S.S. Chen, F. He, "Extreme learning machine for multi-label classification," *Entropy*, vol. 18, id. 225, 2016. DOI: [10.3390/e18060225](https://doi.org/10.3390/e18060225)
102. Y. Xinghuo, M.O. Efe, O. Kaynak, "A general backpropagation algorithm for feedforward neural networks learning," *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.*, vol. 13, pp. 251–254, 2002. DOI: [10.1109/72.977323](https://doi.org/10.1109/72.977323)
103. D.G. Zhang, Y.N. Zhu, C.P. Zhao, W.B. Dai, "A new constructing approach for a weighted topology of wireless sensor networks based on local-world theory for the Internet of Things (IoT)," *Comput.Math.with Appl.*, vol. 64, pp. 1044–1055, 2012. DOI: [10.1016/j.camwa.2012.03.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2012.03.023)
104. W. Meng, W. Li, C. Su, J. Zhou, R. Lu, "Enhancing Trust Management for Wireless Intrusion Detection via Traffic Sampling in the Era of Big Data," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 7234–7243, 2017. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2772294](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2772294)
105. W. Fang, W. Zhang, W. Chen, Y. Liu, C. Tang, "TMSRS: Trust management-based secure routing scheme in industrial wireless sensor network with fog computing," *Wirel.Netw.*, vol. 26, pp. 3169–3182, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11276-019-02129-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11276-019-02129-w)
106. M. Elhoseny, A.E. Hassanien, "Secure data transmission in WSN: An overview," *Stud. Syst. Decis. Control*, vol. 165, pp. 115–143, 2019. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-92807-4_6](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-92807-4_6)
107. F. Hussain, R. Hussain, S.A. Hassan, E. Hossain, "Machine Learning in IoT Security: Current Solutions and Future Challenges," *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials*, vol. 22, pp. 1686–1721, 2020. DOI: [10.1109/COMST.2020.2986444](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2020.2986444)
108. A. Talpur, M. Gurusamy, "Machine Learning for Security in Vehicular Networks: A Comprehensive Survey," *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials*, vol. 24, pp. 346–379, 2021. DOI: [10.1109/COMST.2021.3129079](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2021.3129079)
109. L. Xiao, Y. Li, G. Han, G. Liu, W. Zhuang, "PHY-Layer Spoofing Detection with Reinforcement Learning in Wireless Networks," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 65, pp. 10037–10047, 2016. DOI: [10.1109/TVT.2016.2524258](https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2016.2524258)
110. M. Pundir, J.K. Sandhu, "A Systematic Review of Quality of Service in Wireless Sensor Networks using Machine Learning: Recent Trend and Future Vision," *J. Netw. Comput.Appl.*, vol. 188, id. 103084, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.jnca.2021.103084](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2021.103084)
111. M. Rizwan, A. Shabbir, A.R. Javed, G. Srivastava, T.R. Gadekallu, M. Shabir, M.A. Hassan, "Risk monitoring strategy for confidentiality of healthcare information," *Comput.Electr.Eng.*, vol. 100, id. 107833, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.compeleceng.2022.107833](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2022.107833)
112. S. Roy, J. Li, B.J. Choi, Y. Bai, "A lightweight supervised intrusion detection mechanism for IoT networks," *Futur.Gener.Comput. Syst.*, vol. 127, pp. 276–285, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.future.2021.09.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2021.09.027)
113. A. Ahmed Nacer, C. Godart, G. Rosinosky, S. Tari, S. Youcef, "Business process outsourcing to the cloud: Balancing costs with security risks," *Comput. Ind.*, vol. 104, pp. 59–74, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.compind.2018.10.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2018.10.003)
114. R. Ahmad, R. Wazirali, Q. Bsoul, T. Abu-Ain, W. Abu-Ain, "Feature-Selection and Mutual-Clustering Approaches to Improve DoS Detection and Maintain WSNs' Lifetime," *Sensors*, vol. 21, id. 4821, 2021. DOI: [10.3390/s21144821](https://doi.org/10.3390/s21144821)
115. R. Wazirali, R. Ahmad, "Machine Learning Approaches to Detect DoS and Their Effect on WSNs Lifetime," *Comput.Mater. Contin.*, vol. 70, pp. 4922–4946, 2022. DOI: [10.32604/cmc.2022.020044](https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2022.020044)

116. C. Ioannou, V. Vassiliou, "An Intrusion Detection System for Constrained WSN and IoT Nodes Based on Binary Logistic Regression," in Proceedings of the 21st ACM International Conference on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Wireless and Mobile Systems, Montreal, QC, Canada, 28 October–2 November 2018; pp. 259–263, 2018. DOI: [10.1145/3242102.3242145](https://doi.org/10.1145/3242102.3242145)
117. R. Ul Islam, M.S. Hossain, K. Andersson, "A novel anomaly detection algorithm for sensor data under uncertainty," *Soft Comput.*, vol. 22, pp. 1623–1639, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/s00500-016-2425-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-016-2425-2)
118. B.A. Tama, M. Comuzzi, K.H. Rhee, "TSE-IDS: A Two-Stage Classifier Ensemble for Intelligent Anomaly-Based Intrusion Detection System," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 94497–94507, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2928048](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2928048)
119. P. Gulganwa, S. Jain, "EES-WCA: Energy efficient and secure weighted clustering for WSN using machine learning approach," *Int. J. Inf. Technol.*, vol. 14, pp. 135–144, 2022. DOI: [10.1007/s41870-021-00744-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41870-021-00744-5)
120. D. Wu, Z. Jiang, X. Xie, X. Wei, W. Yu, R. Li, "LSTM Learning with Bayesian and Gaussian Processing for Anomaly Detection in Industrial IoT," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informat.*, vol. 16, pp. 5244–5253, 2020. DOI: [10.1109/TII.2019.2952917](https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2019.2952917)
121. R. Wazirali, R. Ahmad, S. Alhiyari, "SDN-OpenFlow Topology Discovery: An Overview of Performance Issues," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 11, id. 6999, 2021. DOI: [10.3390/app11156999](https://doi.org/10.3390/app11156999)
122. P. Amangele, M.J. Reed, M. Al-Naday, N. Thomos, M. Nowak, "Hierarchical Machine Learning for IoT Anomaly Detection in SDN," in Proceedings of the 2019 International Conference on Information Technologies (InfoTech), Varna, Bulgari, 19–20 September 2019; pp. 19–20, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/InfoTech.2019.8860878](https://doi.org/10.1109/InfoTech.2019.8860878)
123. G. Liu, H. Zhao, F. Fan, G. Liu, Q. Xu, S. Nazir, "An Enhanced Intrusion Detection Model Based on Improved kNN in WSNs," *Sensors*, vol. 22, id.1407, 2022. DOI: [10.3390/s22041407](https://doi.org/10.3390/s22041407)
124. K. ArchanaJanani, V. Vetrivelvi, R. Parthasarathi, V.R.K. Subrahmanya, G. Rao, "An Approach to URL Filtering in SDN," in Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies; Smys, S., Bestak, R., Chen, J.I.-Z., Kotuliak, I., Eds.; Springer: Singapore, pp. 217–228, 2019. DOI: [10.1007/978-981-10-8681-6_21](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-8681-6_21)
125. M. Miao, B. Wu, "A Flexible Phishing Detection Approach Based on Software-Defined Networking Using Ensemble Learning Method," in Proceedings of the 2020 4th International Conference on High Performance Compilation, Computing and Communications, Guangzhou, China, 27–29 June 2020; pp. 70–73, 2020. DOI: [10.1145/3407947.3407952](https://doi.org/10.1145/3407947.3407952)
126. T. Chin, K. Xiong, C. Hu, "Phishlimiter: A Phishing Detection and Mitigation Approach Using Software-Defined Networking," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 42513–42531, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2837889](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2837889)
127. R. Wazirali, R. Ahmad, A.A.K. Abu-Ein, "Sustaining accurate detection of phishing URLs using SDN and feature selection approaches," *Comput.Netw.*, vol. 201, id. 108591, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.comnet.2021.108591](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2021.108591)
128. M. Emperuman, S. Chandrasekaran, "Hybrid continuous density hmm-based ensemble neural networks for sensor fault detection and classification in wireless sensor network," *Sensors*, vol. 20, id. 745, 2020. DOI: [10.3390/s20030745](https://doi.org/10.3390/s20030745)
129. S. Zidi, T. Moulahi, B. Alaya, "Fault detection in wireless sensor networks through SVM classifier," *IEEE Sens. J.*, vol. 18, pp. 340–347, 2018. DOI: [10.1109/JSEN.2017.2771226](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2017.2771226)
130. D.A. Tran, T. Nguyen, "Localization In Wireless Sensor Networks Based on Support Vector Machines," *IEEE Trans. Parallel Distrib. Syst.*, vol. 19, pp. 981–994, 2008. DOI: [10.1109/TPDS.2007.70800](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPDS.2007.70800)
131. Q. Sun, Y. Sun, X. Liu, Y. Xie, X. Chen, "Study on fault diagnosis algorithm in WSN nodes based on RPCA model and SVDD for multi-class classification," *Cluster Comput.*, vol. 22, pp. 6043–6057, 2019. DOI: [10.1007/s10586-018-1793-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-018-1793-z)

132. P. Chanak, I. Banerjee, "Fuzzy rule-based faulty node classification and management scheme for large scale wireless sensor networks," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 45, pp. 307–321, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/j.eswa.2015.09.040](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2015.09.040)
133. X. Yang, X. Chen, R. Xia, Z. Qian, "Wireless sensor network congestion control based on standard particle swarm optimization and single neuron PID," *Sensors*, vol. 18, id. 1265, 2018. DOI: [10.3390/s18041265](https://doi.org/10.3390/s18041265)
134. V. Srivastava, S. Tripathi, K. Singh, L.H. Son, "Energy efficient optimized rate based congestion control routing in wireless sensor network," *J. Ambient Intell. Humaniz. Comput.*, vol. 11, pp. 1325–1338, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s12652-019-01449-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-019-01449-1)
135. S. Qu, L. Zhao, Z. Xiong, "Cross-layer congestion control of wireless sensor networks based on fuzzy sliding mode control," *Neural Comput. Appl.*, vol. 32, pp. 13505–13520, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s00521-020-04758-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-020-04758-1)
136. F.F. Alsharif, E.A. Sundararajan, R. Ahmad, Y. Alkhatib, "New Framework for Authentication and key Establishment to Secure 6LoWPAN Networks," in Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics (ICEEI), Nanjing, China, 3–5 December 2021; IEEE: Selangor, Malaysia, 2021; pp. 1–6, 2021.
137. M.J. Wiener, "Cryptanalysis of short RSA secret exponents," *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci.*, vol. 434 LNCS, id. 372, 1990. DOI: [10.1016/j.ins.2003.08.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2003.08.016)
138. M.D. Lepech, V.C. Li, "Application of ECC for bridge deck link slabs," *Mater. Struct. Constr.*, vol. 42, pp. 1185–1195, 2009. DOI: [10.1617/s11527-009-9544-5](https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-009-9544-5)
139. I. Ullah, A. Alkhalifah, S.U. Rehman, N. Kumar, M.A. Khan, "An Anonymous Certificateless Signcryption Scheme for Internet of Health Things," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 101207–101216, 2021. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3097403](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3097403)
140. A.H. Moon, U. Iqbal, G.M. Bhat, "Light weight Authentication Framework for WSN," in Proceedings of the 2016 International Conference on Electrical, Electronics, and Optimization Techniques (ICEEOT), Chennai, India, 3–5 March 2016; pp. 3099–3105, 2016. DOI: [10.1109/ICEEOT.2016.7755272](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEEOT.2016.7755272)
141. R. Das, A. Gadre, S. Zhang, S. Kumar, J.M.F. Moura, "A Deep Learning Approach to IoT Authentication," in Proceedings of the 2018 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), Kansas City, MO, USA, 20–24 May 2018. DOI: [10.1109/ICC.2018.8422832](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC.2018.8422832)
142. H. Fang, X. Wang, L. Hanzo, "Learning-Aided Physical Layer Authentication as an Intelligent Process," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 67, pp. 2260–2273, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/TCOMM.2018.2881117](https://doi.org/10.1109/TCOMM.2018.2881117)
143. Y. Ashibani, Q.H. Mahmoud, *A Machine Learning-Based User Authentication Model Using Mobile App Data*, Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2020.
144. Y. Ashibani, Q.H. Mahmoud, "A Behavior-Based Proactive User Authentication Model Utilizing Mobile Application Usage Patterns," *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci.*, vol. 11489 LNAI, pp. 284–295, 2019. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-18305-9_23](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-18305-9_23)
145. Y. Ashibani, Q.H. Mahmoud, "User authentication for smart home networks based on mobile apps usage," in Proceedings of the 2019 28th International Conference on Computer Communication and Networks (ICCCN), Valencia, Spain, 29 July–1 August 2019; pp. 1–6, 2019. DOI: [10.1109/ICCCN.2019.8847149](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCN.2019.8847149)
146. J. Canedo, A. Skjellum, "Using machine learning to secure IoT systems," in Proceedings of the 2016 14th Annual Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust (PST), Auckland, New Zealand, 12–14 December 2016; pp. 219–222, 2016. DOI: [10.1109/PST.2016.7906930](https://doi.org/10.1109/PST.2016.7906930)
147. M. Miettinen, S. Marchal, I. Hafeez, N. Asokan, A.R. Sadeghi, S. Tarkoma, "IoT SENTINEL: Automated Device-Type Identification for Security Enforcement in IoT," in Proceedings of the 2017 IEEE 37th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS), Atlanta, GA, USA, 5–8 June 2017; pp. 2177–2184, 2017. DOI: [10.1109/ICDCS.2017.284](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCS.2017.284)

148. Y. Meidan, M. Bohadana, A. Shabtai, J.D. Guarnizo, M. Ochoa, N.O. Tippenhauer, Y. Elovici, "ProfilIoT: A machine learning approach for IoT device identification based on network traffic analysis," in Proceedings of the Symposium on Applied Computing, Marrakech, Morocco, 3–7 April 2017. DOI: [10.1145/3019612.3019878](https://doi.org/10.1145/3019612.3019878)
149. G.D. O'Mahony, P.J. Harris, C.C. Murphy, "Detecting Interference in Wireless Sensor Network Received Samples: A Machine Learning Approach," in Proceedings of the 2020 IEEE 6th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT), New Orleans, LA, USA, 2–16 June 2020. DOI: [10.1109/WF-IoT48130.2020.9221332](https://doi.org/10.1109/WF-IoT48130.2020.9221332)
150. R. Ahmad, E.A. Sundararajan, A. Khalifeh, "A survey on femtocell handover management in dense heterogeneous 5G networks," *Telecommun. Syst.*, vol. 75, pp. 481–507, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11235-020-00718-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11235-020-00718-1)
151. S. Luo, H. Li, Z. Wen, B. Qian, G. Morgan, A. Longo, O. Rana, R. Ranjan, "Blockchain-Based Task Offloading in Drone-Aided Mobile Edge Computing," *IEEE Netw.*, vol. 35, pp. 124–129, 2021. DOI: [10.1109/MNET.011.2000222](https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.011.2000222)
152. S. Abdelwahab, B. Hamdaoui, M. Guizani, T. Znati, "Network function virtualization in 5G," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 54, pp. 84–91, 2016. DOI: [10.1109/MCOM.2016.7452271](https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2016.7452271)
153. A.A. Barakabitze, A. Ahmad, R. Mijumbi, A. Hines, "5G network slicing using SDN and NFV: A survey of taxonomy, architectures and future challenges," *Comput. Netw.*, vol. 167, id. 106984, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.comnet.2019.106984](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2019.106984)
154. B. Isyaku, M.S. MohdZahid, M. BteKamat, K. Abu Bakar, F.A. Ghaleb, "Software Defined Networking Flow Table Management of OpenFlow Switches Performance and Security Challenges: A Survey," *Futur.Int.*, vol. 12, id. 147, 2020. DOI: [10.3390/fi12090147](https://doi.org/10.3390/fi12090147)
155. K. Arulkumaran, M.P. Deisenroth, M. Brundage, A.A. Bharath, "Deep reinforcement learning: A brief survey," *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.*, vol. 34, pp. 26–38, 2017. DOI: [10.1109/MSP.2017.2743240](https://doi.org/10.1109/MSP.2017.2743240)
156. C. Tan, F. Sun, T. Kong, W. Zhang, C. Yang, C. Liu, "A Survey on Deep Transfer Learning," in International Conference on Artificial Neural Networks; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, pp. 270–279, 2018.
157. M. AwaisJaved, S. Zeadally, Z. Hamid, "Trust-based security adaptation mechanism for Vehicular Sensor Networks," *Comput. Netw.*, vol. 137, pp. 27–36, 2018. DOI: [10.1016/j.comnet.2018.03.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2018.03.010)

